

D1.1 PoliRural Vision For Attractive Rural Places & Professions

Project Acronym:	PoliRural	
Project title:	Future Oriented Collaborative Policy Development for Rural Areas and People	
Grant Agreement No.	818496	
Website:	www.polirural.eu	
Contact:	info@polirural.eu	
Version:	2.3	
Date:	28 May 2021	
Responsible Partner:	AREI	
Contributing Partners:	CULS, CCSS, PLAN4ALL, NUVIT, SPU v Nitre, Agroinstitut, CityNitra, OZ VIPA SK, VPR, LLF, NP, GAIA, PSTE, MIGAL, 21C, INNOVAGR, JIIP, VITO, AgFutura, CoO, TRAGSA, SocialInnolabs, HAMK, MAC, MAC, GGP	
Reviewers:	Pavel Kogut – 21c Pavel Simek – CULS	
Dissemination Level:	Public	X
	Confidential – only consortium members and European Commission Services	
Keywords:	Rural areas, attractiveness, vision, needs, challenges.	

Revision History

Revision no.	Date	Author	Organisation	Description
0.1	12/08/2019	Milos Ulman	CULS	Fixed formatting of tables, sample Heading 2 and Heading 3 added.
0.2	4/09/2019	Pavel Kogut	21c	General edits (grammar, punctuation, flow) and formatting
0.3	12/09/2019	Ligita Melece	AREI	Modification of the document after reviewer's comments
1.0	19/09/2019	Ligita Melece	AREI	Final revisions and formatting
2.0	25/03/2021	Armands Pužulis	AREI	Modification of the document after EC reviewer's comments
2.1	26/04/2021	Armands Pužulis	AREI	Modification of the document after reviewers' comments
2.2	28/04/2021	Pavel Kogut	21c	Prefinal checks before submission
2.3	28/05/2021	Milos Ulman	CULS	Final check and submission

Responsibility for the information and views set out in this publication lies entirely with the authors.

Every effort has been made to ensure that all statements and information contained herein are accurate, however the PoliRural Project Partners accept no liability for any error or omission.

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Acronyms and abbreviations

BMEL	Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
CEJA	European Council of Young Farmers
CLLD	Community-led Local Development
CVET	Continuing (Vocational) Education and Training
DG	Directorate-General of the European Commission
DG AGRI	Directorate General for Agriculture and Rural Development
D1.1	Deliverable 1.1
EC	European Commission
EIP	European Innovation Partnership
EIP-AGRI	European Innovation Partnership for Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability
ENRD	European Network for Rural Development
EP	European Parliament
EPRS	European Parliamentary Research Service
ERDF	European Regional Development Fund
Eurofound	European Foundation for the Improvement of Living and Working Conditions
ESF	European Social Fund
ESDN	European Sustainable Development Network
ESPON	European Observation Network, Territorial Development and Cohesion
EU	European Union
GIS	Geographic information system
ICT	Information and communication technology
IPBES	Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services
LAGs	Local Action Groups
LEADER	Liaisons Entre Actions de Development de l'Economie Rurale (Links between actions for the development of the rural economy)
LFSs	Local Food Systems
NEWBIE	New Entrant netWork: Business models for Innovation, entrepreneurship and resilience in European agriculture
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
OECD	Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development
OJ	Official Journal of the European Union
RDP	Rural Development Programme
SME	Small and medium-sized enterprise
SSFC	Short supply food chain
VET	Vocational education and training
WP	Work package

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Executive Summary

This deliverable provides an overview of the implementation of the first stage of Task 1.1 'Envisioning More Attractive Rural Places & Professions'. Within the task, an initial vision (i.e. definition) of rural attractiveness has been created. Main rural assets, rural needs and challenges, as well as opportunities and enablers have been identified. Also, the literature review was conducted.

The study was implemented in several sequential steps: brainstorming (PoliRural partners); literature review; questionnaire survey (PoliRural consortium partners); reporting data summarising and evaluation.

The literature review indicates (showcases a growing interest and) that there is a growing interest and importance in assessing attractiveness of territories, i.e. rural, from the point of view of their stakeholders, especially inhabitants or potential inhabitants, including new entrants. Well-being, quality of life or well-living, as well as contentment with satisfying the needs of the various socio-demographic groups in rural areas is gaining in importance. The economic development, ensuring well-being and well-living of rural inhabitants, can be encouraged by various tools and measures: new forms of entrepreneurship (multifunctional agriculture, tourism, social entrepreneurship, public services, etc.); new forms of networking and cooperation (social innovations, sharing, crowdfunding, etc.); knowledge and innovations (i.e., vocational education and training, lifelong learning and distance learning, local knowledge), promoting the involvement of young people, women, as well as new entrants.

Rural attractiveness is practically not defined, but instead limits itself to descriptions and explanations from various authors. Rural attractiveness is more linked with competitiveness of territories, attractiveness investment, as well as development of tourism. It is largely related to landscapes, their quality and attractiveness. It is generally recognised that territorial capital is a crucial dimension of the attractiveness of places. Therefore, views on it differ, and there also are different factors that constitute attractiveness. Factors and indicators constituting attractiveness are based on territorial capital (i.e. environmental, anthropic, economic, social-cultural, human and institutional capital) and assets. Their choice and assessment can depend on size of territory (state, region, municipality), and on target/stakeholder groups. It can be, for instance, a sector, (e.g. public, NGOs, governmental), field (e.g. agriculture, tourism, forestry, ITC), various socio-demographic groups (inhabitants, new entrants/newcomers, visitors, etc.; age, gender, prosperity and health state, etc.), human, including education level.

PoliRural has a simple, if ambitious, objective - to make rural places and professions more attractive for established rural populations and recent or potential newcomers. The emphasis on more means there is plenty of room for improvement. Indeed, although some rural areas represent the most prosperous and well performing areas in the country, others are experiencing depopulation, demographic ageing, high levels of poverty and land abandonment. Rural attractiveness is about rural development that encompasses the diversity of rural life, places and professions. It is about creating conditions that entice people to invest, relocate, live, work and marry in rural areas. Attractive rural places are valuable environments where biodiversity and natural heritage are safeguarded.

The initial vision of rural attractiveness was developed and offered for further improvement; in particular, its definition, which earned the highest assessment. It is as follows: “Rural attractiveness is sustainable rural communities with access to high quality public services, a thriving and diverse local economy where agriculture related activities are complemented by sustainable tourism and other forms of employment in a working countryside, and an attractive, ecologically rich and accessible countryside in which the environment and biodiversity are conserved and enhanced”.

Recognising that sustainable development in rural areas, in which an economic growth and performance is indisputable basis or fundament for well-being of rural people, including provision of high quality of life, it may be possible to bestow a briefer definition of the attractiveness of rural places, for example: “Rural attractiveness is a viable, healthy and pleasant place to live, work and visit”.

1 Introduction

Due to strong interdependencies (WP1) will influence and will be influenced by the developments in other work packages, especially those where the role of pilots is most pronounced, such as current rural situation (WP4), future rural outlook (WP5) and regional rural change (WP6). WP1 will start with a visioning exercise (M2) and will conclude with practical recommendations for regional stakeholders (M28).

Within the first task of WP1, an initial vision (i.e. definition) of rural attractiveness must be created. This universal definition can later be substituted with regionally adapted concepts of rural attractiveness that better reflects local needs, priorities, sense of identity and vision of the future. Furthermore, main rural assets, rural needs and challenges, as well as opportunities and enablers must be identified.

The attractiveness of the countryside can be viewed from two different perspectives: “public” and “professional”. Professional view is based on the needs and ideas of specific groups of experts. By contrast, the public one is based on public perceptions and therefore reflects the opinion of the society or its groups, which is socially acceptable. In turn, social acceptance can be assessed in terms of culture, territorial differences, interdependence of persons and organizations involved. The attractiveness of the countryside can thus be seen in its diversity. Both views are mutually influential and interdependent.

Upon receiving responses to the PoliRural survey, we found that several items identified by groups during brainstorming (rural attractiveness assets, rural needs and challenges, and rural opportunities and enablers) were marked by question marks and comments showing incomplete information or insufficient understanding. Concepts affected include multifunctional agriculture, short food chain, social innovation, socially responsible business.

This necessitated broader literature review which would include not only the concept of rural attractiveness but also cover a wide range of issues. In our opinion, it is important to improve the understanding of these concepts among the PoliRural participants, which is crucial for smooth and efficient pilot operations.

The D1.1 consists of 4 main parts. The methodology explains the approach to defining rural attractiveness in the PoliRural project and the steps of rural attractiveness initial vision’s development. Literature review is a basic block that forms “professional” views on definition. It is divided into several sections, according to the determinants and contexts of rural attractiveness. The “public” definition is based on the next two chapters. The chapter “Creation of preliminary vision’s definition of rural attractiveness” explains the PoliRural consortium partner workshop (June 20, 2019, Prague) process and results. The chapter “Results of PoliRural partners` questionnaire survey” analyses rural attractiveness vision, definition and specification of rural assets, needs and challenges, and opportunities and enablers.

2 Methodology

Development of PoliRural's vision or vision's definition of rural attractiveness is planned in several stages, each of which takes into account or is based on the results of the development of other work packages (WP) of PoliRural project. Figure 1 shows the four steps of rural attractiveness vision's development, and activities that correspond to the steps. The letter M and the number indicate the month of a project timeline in which the planned activity/task should be performed. As indicated by the arrow symbol above specific steps, those will accompany the development of vision's definition through the whole project in an iterative manner.

Figure 1 The four steps of rural attractiveness vision's development

The role of visions in sustainability research and problem solving has been recognized and visioning has been integrated in comprehensive procedural frameworks leading from problem definition to strategy implementation (Wiek & Iwaniec, 2014). A thorough sustainability visioning process is not a simple and linear construction sequence. There is a need for continuous review, reflection, and revision, in short, for an iterative procedure, in order to produce a high-quality sustainability vision.

The starting point of each visioning process, i.e. the initial creation of vision elements or full vision (vision pool) is, if not entirely based on previous results (document review), a creative act. Furthermore, several vision qualities demand a strong link between analytical and creative techniques. In particular, using sustainability criteria and plausibility criteria for the creation of visions requires intuition, imagination, virtual transfer, and other creative capacities. Wiek and Iwaniec (2014) stress the importance of the creativity techniques, including brainstorming.

Qualitative research begins with assumptions about the possible use of a theoretical lens, and so is concerned with research problems that inquire into the meaning individuals or groups ascribe to a social or human problem (Creswell & Poth, 2017). In qualitative research, multiple forms of data are typically gathered, such as interviews, observations, and documents, rather than relying on a single data source. Then the researchers review all of the data and make sense of them, organising them into categories or themes that cut across all of the data sources.

Inductive data analysis is used to conduct qualitative research, in which patterns, categories, and themes are built from the 'bottom-up'. It may also involve collaborating with the participants interactively, so that they have a chance to shape the themes or abstractions that

emerge from the process (Creswell & Poth, 2017). The development of initial vision's definition of rural attractiveness, as well as identification of assets, needs and challenges, and opportunities and enablers of rural stakeholders is performed in several steps (Figure 2).

Figure 2 The steps of rural attractiveness initial vision's development

The literature preview is a starting point for preparing the workshop which the PoliRural consortium partners attended at the start of the project. The workshop took place during the project's kick-off-meeting on June 20, 2019 in Prague. It included a significant brainstorming component, a method for generating ideas, increasing creative efficacy, or finding solutions to problems (Wilson, 2013). Moreover, brainstorming can be applied any time when new ideas or solutions to problems are required. More detailed methodology regarding the workshop is provided in the Section 4.

A more general, less detailed literature review was performed before preparing the questionnaire survey. Broader literature review, which would include not only the concept of rural attractiveness, but also cover wide range of issues, was initiated by results of the PoliRural survey. Respondents (PoliRural participants) marked with question marks and comments several items (rural attractiveness assets, rural needs and challenges, and rural opportunities and enablers), which were identified in groups during brainstorming. For example, multifunctional agriculture, short food chain, social innovation, socially responsible business, etc. In our opinion, it was necessary to improve i) the understanding of the meaning of these terms among PoliRural participants and ii) pilot operations which are meant to start in September 2019.

A literature review was conducted using qualitative research methods. It was carried out using two review methods: 1) the systematic review approach, using the descriptive and comparative methods (Thomas & Harden, 2008); and 2) integrative review approach including

diverse data sources, which enhance a holistic understanding of the topic of interest (Whittemore & Knafl, 2005). This is a specific review method that summarizes past empirical or theoretical literature to provide a more comprehensive understanding of a particular phenomenon or problem. This has the potential to create an initial vision of rural areas' attractiveness, as well as to raise awareness of rural stakeholders' needs and challenges (e.g. residents and especially newcomers, young people, etc.) presented by scholars, experts and research projects' results, practice, and policy initiatives (i.e. EU and international institutions). A professionally done integrative review can present the state of the science, contribute to theory development, and have direct applicability to practice and policy (Whittemore & Knafl, 2005). Integrative reviews include diverse data sources, which enhance a holistic understanding of the topic of interest. However, combining diverse data sources is complex and challenging. The review has a 5-stage process including the following: (i) identification of the problem and purpose of the review; (ii) a structured literature search; (iii) data evaluation; (iv) data analysis; and (v) presentation of findings (Wilding et al., 2012).

Additionally, the inductive analysis was used, which Thomas and Harden (2008) refer to as "approaches that primarily use detailed readings of raw data to derive concepts, themes, or a model through interpretations made from the raw data." A common approach to the interpretation of meanings of textual data is carried out by means of content analysis (Vaismoradi et al., 2013), which is used as a common approach to the interpretation of meanings from textual data (Seuring & Gold, 2012). De-contextualisation and theory-led abstraction of the content analysis outcomes allow one to claim a certain degree of generalization of the findings. For the said review, the following sources had been chosen:

- academic literature, mainly indexed in Scopus, WoS database and Open Access (i.e., via Google Scholar);
- research reports of various institutions, mainly EU level;
- EU subject-related research projects outcomes;
- EU legislation, strategies, programs, guides, recommendations, etc.

The methodology of the literature review was based on following inclusion principles: sources should very recent; papers are in English; if possible, scholars/authors' research was performed in Europe or related to European issues. In turn, the exclusion principles were as follows: research or study is devoted to a very narrow or specific issue; the study was carried out in a very small territory or specific area (e.g. small islands).

A questionnaire survey, which is ease and flexibility of use, compared to other methods of data collection (Akinici & Saunders, 2015), of our research was designed (i) to choose the most appropriate vision's definition, which better characterized rural attractiveness; (ii) to identify rural assets; and (iii) to identify needs and challenges, opportunities and enablers of rural areas. The survey was conducted from July 12 to July 23, 2019. Questionnaire was sent by email to all PoliRural consortium participants (legal entities), because all of them are involved in WP 1 Task 1.1. Reporting data (completed questionnaires) received from PoliRural partners were summarized, complimented and analysed. The data of prioritization of rural attractiveness vision's definition were analysed by descriptive statistics (Jackson, 2015). To evaluate the reporting data of rural assets, needs and challenges, and opportunities and enablers, qualitative research methods were used, such as content analysis.

3 Literature review

The literature review has been conducted to obtain a reasonable overview of the interrelated objectives/ tasks: (i) attractiveness, particularly rural, as well as related factors (e.g. quality of life) and resources (e.g. rural or territorial capital, rural assets); (ii) activities and opportunities to increase the rural attractiveness, which have been indicated by PoliRural participants (such as rural needs and challenges, and rural opportunities and enablers) during brainstorming. The sources were contributions of scholars (e.g. academic literature), subject-related project results, and guides and recommendations of different EU institutions (European Parliament and Council, EC, EU level organizations etc.). To our mind, such overview can help PoliRural participants better understand the challenges of sustainable rural development and possibilities for conducting pilot activities.

Rural attractiveness is being viewed in separate sections of this chapter, where various factors or contexts that are relevant to rural attractiveness are discussed. There are eight sections in total and they deal with: 1) an explanation of the core concepts and concept of rural attractiveness; 2) quality of life which is closely related to the attractiveness of the countryside; 3) territorial capital and rural assets, is the prism through which the attractiveness of the countryside as a whole is viewed; 4) knowledge and innovation; 5) ecosystem services overlooking natural capital; 6) multifunctionality of agriculture and farm diversification as an important economic basis for the rural environment; 7) social aspects; and 8) social innovations of rural areas (Figure 3).

Ch. 3 sections	Contexts and factors of rural attractiveness	
The core concepts Rural attractiveness Quality of life; Territorial capital and rural assets; Knowledge and innovation; Ecosystem services; Multifunctionality of agriculture and farm diversification; Social aspects in rural areas; Social innovations and innovative activities.	Rural; Rural development; Diversity; Local capital; The role of people; Determinants of migration; Objective and subjective factors of rural attractiveness; Volume and quality of services; Value-based needs; Landscapes; Public goods; Lifelong learning; Local knowledge; ICT; Entrepreneurship;	Ecosystems; Rural community, Social capital; Social entrepreneurship; Care farming; Creative industries and tourism; Local food systems; Social farming; Social innovation; Women; Young people; New entrants; Corporate social responsibility; Crowdfunding; Policy.

Figure 3 Contexts and factors of rural attractiveness

The chapter 3 covers a number of contexts and factors relevant to rural attractiveness. These contexts make it possible to further define the needs of pilot regions based on the concept of rural attractiveness.

3.1 The core concepts

Rural attractiveness is closely related to rural development, regional development, and cultural contexts. In turn, rural development and regional development are connotations of

development. The understanding of development is rooted in the cultural context and public perceptions that have changed over time, forming different theories about development. The concepts under consideration are also conditional on politics. The understanding of rural development is characterized by the diverse differences of rural areas, which are reflected in different rural typologies.

The concept of rural development has a dual nature. Nederveen Pieterse (2010) defines development as improvement of situation and the organized intervention in collective affairs. Gradually development is becoming a multilevel, multiscale series of efforts, simultaneously taking place at different levels. The concept of development has historically been centred on the economics and as such is associated with socio-economic growth. Growth is not always the objective per se, but a means for achieving well-being, according to the social, economic, cultural and political conditions of particular populations in specific places (Pike et al., 2017).

Rural development is closely linked to the rural understanding of rural areas and regions. There is no common understanding of rural areas in different countries and in the EU as a whole. Different territorial and policy approaches require different regions to be defined and distinguished. They are always linked to the purpose for which they are intended. OECD rural areas are defined on the basis of the following criteria: population density and distance from major urban centres. Rural areas can be further characterized according to various additional criteria stemming from different aspects of rurality - geographical, social, economic and cultural, resulting in different geographic coverage, with important policy implications (Diakosavvas, 2006). By analysing different typologies, we obtain a mosaic of territories that can be viewed as a conglomerate of diversity, depending on the criteria we select.

The concept of rural development is traditionally associated with rural-urban dualism, but in a political sense with the dualism of rural and agricultural policy. The literature emphasizes mutual interdependency, interconnection making urban-rural continuum. It is often not so easy to draw the line between urban and rural, especially in suburban areas.

This is also reflected in politics. Re-territorialization is an important dimension of what the OECD postulates as the 'New Rural Paradigm' (NRP) in Europe. According to the OECD, this paradigm includes a new, multisectoral, place-based approach to rural development that claims a need for closer links between the rural and urban economy, and to see rural development as a close interplay with regional development more generally (Horlings & Marsden, 2014; OECD, 2006). The trend is that agriculture policy has a modest impact on the future viability of rural areas. The heterogeneity of rural areas' challenges and potentials calls for tailor-made policies (Diakosavvas, 2006). Rural development is perceived as a special business that includes rural life, characterized by a sense of community, working together and social change (Steiner & Atterton, 2015 p. 43).

Previous policies have not succeeded in reducing territorial inequalities. New ways are being sought to address this. The role of personal motivation in development processes, individual and collective role in development, the concept of culture in space and social environment, alternative development perspectives - all this results in new research directions - behavioural economics. Economic geography and political economy are being used to understand how individual and collective behaviour determines the results of regional development (Huggins

& Thompson, 2016; Lee, 2017). Currently, the economy is reintegrating ethics in development conceptualization.

Rural development is associated with 'Quality of life' (QOL), which includes many material and immaterial aspects. It should be emphasized that QOL does not simply refer to income-related living standards of individuals (the economic aspect), but is a broader concept that also includes the surrounding environment, physical and mental health, education, leisure, recreation, social belonging, and so forth (Brauer & Dymitrow, 2014).

Rural development concepts are related to several contexts and areas, the most important of which are: politics, territorial scales, social and cultural contexts, quality of life. Rural development can be seen as a political and socially rooted concept at the same time. This is reflected in the definition of rural areas and rural areas at different scales, in the development of classifications, in the definition of policy approaches, and in the changing perceptions of what rural areas are and what contexts and areas they cover. QOL is such a concept that is highly socially conditioned and characterizes the attractiveness of the countryside.

3.2 Attractiveness of rural areas

The section explains the understanding of rural attractiveness based on the context of territory, competitiveness, local capital, human and business, rural areas and subjectivity.

Whilst attractiveness is not explicitly discussed in EU policy documents, diversity is considered to be a factor of attractiveness that can be utilised to promote growth and territorial cohesion by both attracting investments and mobile populations whilst retaining existing residents (Russo et al., 2012b). A key underlying assumption is that by focusing, and building, on the (diverse) strengths of places more harmonious development can be achieved. Thus attractiveness is conceived as a precondition or an essential dimension of competitiveness, yet this policy narrative is to some extent ambiguous (Russo et al., 2012b).

Attractiveness of a place represents a variety and complexity of factors (Lysgard & Cruickshank, 2013). Hamri et al. (2014) note that the attractiveness of a territory is built on interrelated components, as well as on many and diverse factors, which are geographic, economic, and human and historical. It is stressed that it is a territory's cultural appeal that creates a personal, unique and distinct space and therefore an attractive; and is based on its own values, identity, character, heritage, sensitivity and the expertise of its people, etc. Servillo et al. (2012) argue that territorial capital is a crucial dimension of the attractiveness of places. It is intended as a complex system of natural and socioeconomic elements, defining the uniqueness of local assets. Four elements of the 'static capital' of a place are the economic, institutional, physical and social environment. Therefore, the attractiveness of a place stems from the combination of different assets and from the way(s) they are mobilised, both by governmental and non-governmental organisations (NGOs) and by institutional actors (sectoral stakeholders, NGOs, etc.). This approach offers a dynamic perspective on territorial capital, since the relationship between assets and attractiveness is potentially mutually reinforced through a continuous process of mobilisation that seeks to enhance the existing stock of assets. In this context, governance arrangements are crucial to the mobilisation and use of assets (Servillo et al., 2012). This requires the existence of links, often articulated through organisational arrangements (for example, partnerships) between stakeholders, local

authorities, agencies and citizens, in order to identify, create and mobilise assets and develop policies to achieve specific (attractive) strategies.

Neuschmid et al. (2013) provide a framework definition of attractiveness “...as the interaction of a complex set of characteristics based on the presence/absence of certain forms of territorial capital with the attraction of various ‘audiences’ varying in their level of transience in place from long-term residents as working population to short-term visitors and some hybrids mobilities between the two”. In this sense, attractiveness becomes “a place-specific asset that guarantees some kind of socio-economic stability”. Nature’s benefits to people include the provision of biodiversity and ecosystems (Diaz et al., 2015). By definition, all of nature’s benefits have human value, which can range from spiritual inspiration to market value. Most benefits, however, depend on the joint contribution of nature and anthropogenic assets (Diaz et al., 2015), and provide to people good quality of life.

‘Attractiveness’ is a complex and multifaceted set of characteristics; the relative balance of factors vary depending on the groups that are at the centre of attraction strategies (Servillo et al., 2012). A key component of research into regional development, therefore, is identification of the roles of environmental, physical and social attributes in reinforcing (or diminishing) the attractiveness of regions for each group. Barbovic et al. (2018) conclude that attractiveness is concentrated always around two main factors: 1) human factor on one side, and 2) business factor on the other, where the human – business sphere can be perfectly mixed with time factors. Several scholars provide various definitions or descriptions of attractiveness, particularly of territories, which are presented in Table 1.

	Definition or description	Reference
Attractiveness	quality of life and also socio-institutional parameters (social capital, governance) and features of the organisation of the local productive system (local networks)	ESPON, 2009
	is capacity to durably attract different forms of resources (human, economic and financial).	
	for population: quality of life and liveability (i.e., occupation opportunities, accessibility (i.e., public and private social services), naturalness, quality of governance, hazards and security	Spinalis et al., 2009
	for enterprises: economic motivation (e.g., policies), availability & quality of human resources; access to ICT, economic and social infrastructures (public and private); size of local market, quality of governance, quality of environment (i.e., providing abundant resources), hazards and security	
	is a complex and multifaceted set of characteristics; the relative balance of factors that attract varies depending on the groups that are at the centre of attraction strategies (high-skilled workers, second-home owners, tourists, and so on)	Servillo et al., 2012
	internal attractiveness that assumes the capacity of retaining the reached level of development, attractiveness and population already residing on a certain territory	Zivkovic et al., 2015
	external attractiveness that assumes the capacity for internationalization, that is, attracting new development, residents and investments on a certain territory	
	is a social, political, economic, environmental mentality	Barbovic et al., 2018
relates to that on territorial quality, particularly territorial capital		

Table 1 Definition or description of attractiveness

The attractiveness of rural areas has often been described as the rural idyll. Elshof et al. (2017) argue that mainly social aspects are associated with the rural idyll, such as friendly people, a less hurried lifestyle, and less crime. However, characteristics that are less related to the rural idyll have also been shown to motivate moves to rural areas, such as cheap housing and proximity to family and friends (Bijker et al., 2012; Elshof et al., 2017). Spilanis et al. (2011) confirm that the goal to achieve the highest value impact for the territory, increasing its attractiveness for both residence and entrepreneurship. The findings of the EUROISLANDS project on the attractiveness factors reveal that islanders consider the quality of the health care system, trip frequency, job opportunities, regularity of water supply, quality of life and quality of education as the most important factors of attractiveness for living. The most important factors for businesses are trip frequency, economic incentives, regularity of water supply, development vision of local authorities, regularity of energy supply and travel cost (Spilanis et al., 2011). The foregoing benefits form the basis for various definitions of rural attractiveness (Table 2).

	Definition or description	Reference
Rural attractiveness	income levels, possibilities for employment and income creation, physical infrastructure, social capital and quality of the environment	OECD, 2001
	healthy air quality, clean, well-maintained environment, low noise, places to walk nearby, wildlife protection, low traffic congestion, attractive countryside, excellent drinking-water quality	Brereton et al., 2011
	is sustainable rural communities with access to high quality public services, a thriving and diverse local economy where agriculture related activities are complemented by sustainable tourism and other forms of employment in a working countryside, and an attractive, ecologically rich and accessible countryside in which the environment and biodiversity are conserved and enhanced	Scott et al., 2011
	stems from a combination of different assets and from the way(s) they are mobilized, both by governmental and non-governmental organizations (NGOs) and by institutional actors (sectoral stakeholders, NGOs, etc.)	Servillo et al., 2012
	Rural Europe is of vibrant, inclusive and sustainable rural communities, supported by diversified rural economies and by effective stewardship of high-quality environment and cultural heritage.	European Rural Parliament, 2015
	is the image that population groups have for an area, based on estimated qualities and characteristics of the areas and their populations, such as accessibility, remoteness, dynamism, competitiveness, research and development, human resources, infrastructures, services available and more	DG AGRI, 2017
	rural idyll; a desire for space, quiet, greenery, and safety	Elshof et al., 2017
	capacity of certain territorial capitals and assets to attract and retain target groups (tourists, residents, migrants and companies or investments) by already existing or developed advantages	Barbovic et al., 2018

Table 2 Definition or description of rural or territorial attractiveness

Over the past few decades, the interest among scholars in the role of amenities in migration has been increasing. The natural qualities of the living environment have often been considered to be amenities that influence moving behaviour. Half-open landscapes, nearby

beaches and other aspects of scenic beauty have all been found to attract people. A desire for space, quiet, greenery, and safety can motivate people to move from urban to rural areas; a trend known as counter-urbanisation (Elshof et al., 2017).

Despite the fact that in many cases the definition of rural attractiveness is not proposed by researchers involved in rural attractiveness assessment or evaluation, several studies provide beneficial characteristics or aspects of rural attractiveness (Table 3).

Aspects or reasons of rural attractiveness	Reference
Relations with family and friends, emotional well-being, material well-being, health, work and productive activity, feeling part of one's local community, personal safety	Pospech et al., 2009
rural landscapes, natural environment, calm, peacefulness, security, existence of attractive towns, nearby, existence of strong networks, good housing conditions, many job opportunities, large offer of sport activities	Shucksmith, 2010
A clean environment, healthy lifestyle, clean fresh air and less traffic, more space, privacy, peacefulness; a sense of community and safeness	Brereton et al., 2011
Less air pollution and noise, lower crime rates, farming possibilities, healthy active lifestyle, community – social life, less traffic, decrease in stress levels, children's education	Brewer, 2016
Spacious housing and varied home-based activities in a natural and peaceful environment, communality, societal involvement, safety and nature, and a safe and natural environment for the children (wishes of young people)	Kuhmonen et al., 2016
Half-open landscapes, nearby beaches and other aspects of scenic beauty, social aspects such as friendly people, a less hurried lifestyle, and less crime; cheap housing and proximity to family and friends	Elshof et al., 2017
Lower population densities, lower pollution or lower criminality levels	Bernard, 2018
Fresh air and wide open spaces, reconnect with nature, peace and quiet, great outdoor living and a healthier lifestyle, good place to raise children, slower pace of living, a less stressful life, part of the community, neighbours, new friends, fresh local food, less crime, a great place to retire	Coutis, 2019

Table 3 Characteristics of rural attractiveness and related aspects

ATTREG has interpreted territorial attractiveness as a characteristic of places that varies spatially according to its constituting natural and environmental, social, cultural and economic components (Russo et al., 2012b). Therefore, achieving place attractiveness means finding the right balance in territorial endowments depending on the groups that are the object of attraction strategies e.g. high skilled workers, second homeowners, tourists (Russo et al., 2012b). From this perspective on regional development the ATTREG has identified the roles of environmental, physical and social attributes in reinforcing (or diminishing) the attractiveness of regions for each group.

A strategic approach to attractiveness is based on the identification of what brings about changes in how a place is perceived and trends in population mobility, the consideration of the different ways in which assets can be utilised to make places “different” and “unique”, the analysis of problems and opportunities in the retention of specific groups, and the development of longer-term strategic and integrated policies that simultaneously address a number of different issues and audiences in order to enhance the attractiveness of a place through the creation of new development paths and visions (Russo et al., 2012b).

Auclair and Vanoni (2017) indicate that the attractiveness of a region, particularly rural area, is partly due to its “natural” or “objective” features, but also to the policies which have been conducted locally. Certainly, rural development policies concern both the rural territories and the populations that live there. Therefore, local development policies, programmes and projects cannot be developed and undertaken without taking into account the characteristics of the population, as well as those of the territory itself. But a territory does not only present objective conditions of life and opportunities (Auclair & Vanoni, 2017). The inhabitants, particularly the young people, develop their own perception of the region in which they live (Figure 4).

Figure 4 Factors influencing people's perception of rural areas²

Eimermann (2015) concludes that individuals move either part-time or full-time to places which offer the potential of a better quality of life. Different notions of ‘attractiveness’ and how places may engage in development processes based on the attraction and retention of human capital, are considered the targets of attraction policies. This approach offers a dynamic perspective on territorial capital, since the relationship between assets and attractiveness is potentially mutually reinforced through a continuous process of mobilisation that seeks to enhance the existing stock of assets.

Quality of life This section explains the quality of life based on living conditions, people's needs, social exclusion and the need for services.

Since the quality of life, as well as criteria thereof, is more or less identified with rural attractiveness, this issue is reviewed separately from other social aspects and issues (see section 4.7). The criteria of quality of life, well-being and well-living are most often used by researchers as factors of attractiveness (Mainet & Edouard, 2017). Well-being and well-living are linked to individual and personal aspects of life through elements of living conditions and standards (material and objective criteria) combined with value systems that match the needs,

² Source: based on Auclair & Vanoni, 2017

demands and priorities of individuals and families. Quality of life based on local amenities and appreciation by the inhabitants, especially newcomers, is a key factor for residential choice. Quality of life therefore refers to living conditions depending on the quality of space and opportunities for the well-being of inhabitants, such as public spaces, access to services, etc. (Mainet & Edouard, 2017). Costanza et al. (2007) argue that quality of life is the extent to which objective human needs are fulfilled in relation to personal or group perceptions of subjective well-being, where human needs are basic needs for subsistence, reproduction, security, affection, etc. (Figure 5).

Figure 5 Quality of life as opportunities, needs and well-being interactions³

Nevertheless, it is recognized by ESPON (2006) that 'quality of life' is hard to define and that social dimension is important, encompassing concerns for social inclusion, gender equality and fair access to the social and cultural services on which residents depend. At the same time, a range of natural and technological hazards also threatens the quality of life. The well-being of regional and rural inhabitants is a crucial policy issue (OECD, 2017). Quality of life factors range from income and jobs to education and civic participation. Many of the most influential factors for people's well-being are local issues such as employment, access to health services, pollution and security. OECD (2017) considers that improving lives entails making the places where people live better. A declining population results in a growing mismatch between the supply and demand of services, creating difficulties for both the public and private sectors. As a result of weak local markets, services become underutilised, poorly maintained and often become unviable and have to be withdrawn (ESPON, 2017).

The loss of population reduces the amount of money circulating within a community, which then affects the viability of local businesses, shops, and transport links. This is further compounded by the eventual loss of medical services, banks, schools and other facilities (EESC, 2016). As local living conditions and quality of life deteriorate, unemployment rises and skilled labour becomes scarce, causing the emergence of abandonment and obsolescence. This further erodes the attractiveness of a region and the rotation of a downward spiral of

³ Source: based on Costanza et al., 2007

demographic decline through falling fertility rates and an enforced aging of the remaining population (ESPON, 2017).

It is stressed in the Declaration of the Cork 2.0 Conference (European Commission, 2016a) that to prevent further rural exodus and youth drain, it is necessary to ensure that rural areas and communities (countryside, farms, villages, small towns etc.) remain attractive places to live and work by improving access to services. OECD (2017) notes that it is necessary to develop an alternative delivery mechanism for assuring the public services in rural areas. Where the demand for services is widely dispersed, it could be more efficient to bring the service to the user. For example, adopting mobile service delivery approaches – bookmobiles that bring library services to communities that are too small to have a physical library, or mobile dental clinics. The Internet offers the possibility to provide services in rural areas and for providers in rural areas to offer services outside their immediate territory. Telemedicine allows x-rays and other diagnostic services conducted in rural areas to be processed and analysed elsewhere. Offering digital services in rural areas is hampered by poor broadband and this is a major issue that threatens to limit growth and development of SMEs.

Various deficiencies have been found to increase social exclusion in rural areas: particularly accessibility of public services and their quality, including educational services, childcare and social services; constrained access to public transport (Brereton et al., 2011; OECD, 2017; Bernard, 2018; Moser et al., 2018). Impact of RDP 2007-2013 measures on ‘improving the quality of life’ in Germany was evaluated by Moser et al. (2018). It was concluded that it was difficult to evaluate the effects of policies on the quality of life in rural areas, because the structure of the RDP and their measures differ considerably, and indicators were missing. It was proposed that the subjective assessments should also be investigated, and assessment of life satisfaction should be carried out using surveys. Nevertheless, Moser et al. (2018) conclude that the measures focused on services and communal facilities should be supported.

However, not all rural areas are the same. The opposite tendencies are observed in suburban or densely populated areas. The opposite processes take place there – as people move from cities to the countryside, conflict situations develop that affect natural values and the landscape. Industries that are typical of the urban environment are entering the countryside, with agriculture playing a smaller role. The functional links between urban and rural also change. This allows us to talk about a space that is completely different from remote peripherals. The term “rural” must now be considered alongside the term “peri-urban” in order to define areas where there are various degrees of interpenetration of city and country, but without a clear distinction between the two (Torre, Wallet, 2016).

European Parliament (2018) stresses that the basis for improving the quality of life in rural areas is the availability of infrastructure such as transport links, access to high-speed broadband Internet, including mobile data services and energy provision, as well as quality social, health and educational services.

Brereton et al. (2011) evaluate individual well-being of rural residents in Ireland, where most important characteristics of quality of life are as follows: healthy air quality, clean, well-maintained environment, low noise, places to walk nearby, wildlife protection, low traffic congestion and attractive countryside. Healthy air quality and excellent drinking-water quality

are the two highest-rated attributes. However, newcomers often have higher expectations regarding local services and are more reluctant to accept a lack of quality in service provision than long-term residents, who probably have been supported by family and social networks. In general, rural areas are characterized by fewer employment opportunities, lower incomes, further distance from public facilities and services than urban areas. At the same time, rural residents have lower housing costs, lower crime and more opportunities to realize their 'ideal home' (Brereton et al., 2011). The BMEL (2015) is committed to furthering Germany's rural regions, where the aim is a sustainable development of rural areas with:

- good quality of life, sufficient basic supplies and efficient infrastructure,
- a high level of economic and innovative strength and good jobs,
- upkeep and conservation of cultivated landscapes and natural resources,
- great recreational value,
- strong civic involvement.

European Council of Young Farmers (2017) stresses the need to address the physical and mental health, safety and welfare of farmers through training, education and innovation, to ensure adequate awareness of health and safety risks on farms. Therefore, the creation of a free yearly health and well-being check-up and a free mandatory health and safety course for every active farmer is required.

3.3 Territorial capital and rural assets

The section looks at the concept of territorial capital in relation to rural assets in relation to territorial capital, development, rural community, landscapes and public goods. Territorial capital is considered one of the cornerstones of rural attractiveness.

Camagni and Capello (2013) point out that territorial capital appears to be a useful concept, which encompasses a wide variety of territorial assets, both tangible and intangible, of a private, public or mixed nature. These assets may be physically produced (public and private goods), supplied by history, or derived from natural endowment (cultural and natural resources, both implying maintenance and control costs). Furthermore, authors propose the concept's definition as follows: "territorial capital may be seen as the set of localized assets – natural, human, artificial, organisational, relational and cognitive – that constitute the competitive potential of a given territory." But Russo et al. (2012b) conclude that the presence of the necessary territorial capital does not automatically lead to attraction and retention of population or economic development.

Van der Ploeg and Mardsen (2008) provide an idea that territorial capital is a public good within a rural community, since those belonging to the community can benefit from it. Jones et al. (2016), recognizing five types of capital: natural, human, produced, social and financial, also add a sixth one – cultural capital. Neuschmid et al. (2013) identify similar dimensions of territorial capital (environmental; economic and human; anthropic; socio-cultural and institutional capitals). Jones et al. (2016) suggest the following definitions of various capitals.

- Natural capital has been variously defined as the stock of physical assets in the environment (water, trees, minerals, species etc.), as well as the processes (e.g. water purification, climate regulation) from which benefits are obtained.
- Other capitals have been named as 'Human-derived' capital, which is an umbrella term encapsulating the following forms of capital:

- Produced capital, also called built capital, manufactured or reproducible capital which consists of manufactured assets, such as roads, vehicles, houses, machinery etc.
- Human capital, defined as the productive capacity of human beings, and encompasses the stock of capabilities held by individuals such as knowledge, education, training, skills as well as physical and mental characteristics e.g. behavioural habits and physical and mental health.
- Social capital, which refers to the stock of contacts, trust, reciprocity and mutual understanding associated with social networks.
- Cultural capital, which refers to the broader factors that allow to interact with each other and the environment, including values and beliefs, socially held knowledge as well as socio-political institutions.
- Financial capital, which is money that facilitates the interaction of other forms of capital by funding the activities that might be required for the services to be realised, managed, or improved.

Servillo et al. (2012) divide the physical elements into anthropic capital (the man-made elements, where agents can have decisional responsibilities) and environmental capital, which is a combination of ecosystem characteristics, such as climate and landscapes. Moreover, the distinction between human and social capital, and cultural capital, highlights the education, knowledge and diversity of social network capacity. Institutional capital has both features of attractiveness and attributes necessary for the mobilisation of assets (Russo et al., 2010). Phillips (2016) argues that as a common subject social capital is constituted through social interactions and connections that have a network character.

Some scholars point out that capitals and assets are the same (Soones, 2009; Speranza et al., 2014). Controversially, other authors hold a different view, believing that it is assets that are derived from capital (Camagni & Capello, 2013; Jones et al., 2016). In other words, the capital consists of various assets.

For instance, Speranza et al. (2014) point out that human capital, natural capital, financial capital, social capital and physical capital are assets. Besides, natural capital has elements of nature that directly or indirectly produce value for people, including ecosystems, species, freshwater, land, minerals, air and, as well as natural processes and functions (Smith et al., 2017). The similarity of rural assets and the territorial capital is emphasised by several scholars, who note that territorial capital can also be identified as an asset (Van der Ploeg & Marsden, 2008; Grieve et al., 2011; Neuschmid et al., 2013; Straka, & Tuzova, 2016; Barboric et al., 2018). Despite that, the terms or names of some territorial capital, which are proposed by the above mentioned scholars, are different. This allows to develop the chart of rural assets or territorial capital as follows (Figure 6).

Figure 6 Rural assets or territorial capital of rural areas⁴

Diaz et al. (2015) describe the anthropogenic assets, which refer to knowledge, technology, financial assets, built infrastructure, etc.

The outside world brings other assets, including capital, market-access, new business practices and knowledge. Thus, development can be seen as a process whereby local assets are developed with the assistance of outside assets to produce new wealth-generating activities (Euracademy Association, 2009). This approach is known as Asset-based Rural Community Development and is rapidly becoming a keyway of seeing the rural development process and of providing a way to operationalize and materialize the need for sustainable development in a way that rural communities can gain benefit. The list of rural capitals and assets, which are based on recommendations of the Euracademy Association (2009), are presented in Table 4.

⁴ Source: based on Van der Ploeg & Marsden, 2008; Grieve et al., 2011; Neuschmid et al., 2013; Straka, & Tuzova, 2016

Capital	Assets
Natural	Biodiversity
	Landscape character
	Soils
	Water
	Air and climate
	Minerals and other non-renewables
Human	Employment and skills base
	Education and training
	Health and well-being
Social	Leadership and trust
	Community cohesion and sense of place
	Stakeholder networks and processes
	Archaeology
	Buildings and built heritage
Manufactured	Transport infrastructure, traffic and access networks
	Processes and waste products
	Energy production and consumption
	IT and telecommunications
Financial	Public funding, e.g., for CAP or rural regeneration
	Local authority expenditure
	Conservation funding
	Local and extra-local business investment
	Other (such as match funding)

Table 4 Rural capital and assets⁵

OECD (2016) underlines that key assets in rural areas are a clean environment, attractive landscapes, cultural and, particularly in Europe, gastronomic heritage. Potential economic opportunities include green tourism packages and promoting local products. Besides, by cultivating their natural and cultural assets, regions have the opportunity to improve their per capita income.

As result of compilation, the schematic relations of rural attractiveness, capitals and assets/indicators are presented in Figure 7.

⁵ Source: based on Euracademy Association, 2009

Figure 7 Rural attractiveness, capitals and assets/indicators⁶

Governance and its quality are recognised as crucial to the mobilisation and use of assets by Russo et al. (2012a). It is stressed that this requires the existence of links, often articulated through organisational arrangements (e.g. partnerships) between stakeholders, local authorities, agencies and citizens in order to identify, create and mobilise assets and develop policies to achieve specific (attractive) strategies (Russo et al., 2012a).

Barboric et al. (2018) note that landscape capital is a new concept that cannot be defined easily; and refers to the same definition proposed in the European Landscape Convention: “Landscape means an area, as perceived by people, whose character is the result of the action and interaction of natural and/or human factors.” Authors confirm that landscapes plays an important public interest role in the cultural, ecological, environmental and social fields; they also constitute a resource favourable to economic activity (protection, management, planning etc.) can contribute to job creation (Barbovic et al., 2018). Therefore, the services that a landscape provides can be:

- Cultural – it represents part of the cultural heritage;
- Ecological – it can give shelter to many different species;
- Environmental – it can contribute to the mitigation of air pollution;
- Social – it contributes to human well-being;
- Economical – it can be part of a tourist route;
- Esthetical – it adds esthetical values to a city/country.

Russo et al. (2010) report that enhancement of territorial attractiveness can be realised through the mobilisation of assets, such as:

- Environmental assets – characterised by indicators regarding geographical and landscape characteristics, landscape quality and attractiveness, settlement structures, and climate;
- Economic and human capital assets – variables relating to the nature of labour market demand, investment, labour supply variables relating to the nature of labour market demand, investment, and labour supply;
- Anthropic assets – indicators of quality of the built environment, accessibility data, cultural heritage and other tourism attractions indicators, etc.;

⁶ Source: based on Russo et al., 2012b; Servillo et al., 2012; Jones et al., 2016; Barbovic et al., 2018

- Social and cultural assets – socio-attitudinal data derived from survey, social composition variables, life expectancy and other social data, plus socio-cultural variables, etc.;
- Institutional assets – variables and indicators that can be interpreted as the level and efficiency of public spending (i.e. levels of service or levels of employment in the public sector), the potential impact of public policy on attractiveness.

It is interesting that Russo with co-authors in the latest report in 2012 re-name these assets as territorial capitals (Russo et al., 2012b). In a classification of public goods associated with agriculture, a distinction is made between environmental and social public goods (Mantino & Vanni, 2018). The most significant environmental public goods identified, although with different level of ‘publicness’, were agricultural landscapes, farmland biodiversity, water quality, water availability, soil functionality, climate stability (greenhouse gas emissions), climate stability (carbon storage), air quality, resilience to flooding and fire. The social public goods included were food security, rural vitality and farm animal welfare and health. However, such functions and services cannot be considered as strictly public goods, but rather societal aspirations (Mantino & Vanni, 2018).

3.4 Knowledge and innovations

The section explains the role of knowledge and innovation in the attractiveness of rural areas. Vocational education and training, non-formal education, lifelong learning, multidisciplinary knowledge and skills, youth, cooperation models, newcomers, local knowledge, the link between knowledge and business, ICT and innovation are analysed.

The new opportunities to rural development are presented by asset-based approaches, which can increase the importance of non-formal learning (Euracademy Association, 2009). Vocational education and training (VET) are a key element of lifelong learning systems, which provide inhabitants with knowledge, skills and competences required in particular occupations and on the labour market. VET responds to the needs of the economy, but also provides learners with skills important for personal development and active citizenship. VET can also boost enterprise performance, competitiveness, and research and innovation, and is a central aspect of successful employment and social policy (European Commission, 2016b)

Education and, therefore, training in rural areas are supported by ‘Continuing education and training (CVET)’ (EESC, 2016). CVET means “...education or training after initial education and training – or after entry into working life aimed at helping individuals to improve or update their knowledge and/or skills; acquire new skills for a career move or retraining; continue their personal or professional development. Continuing education and training is part of lifelong learning and may encompass any kind of education (general, specialised or vocational, formal or informal). It is crucial for the employability of individuals.”

Rural CVET can offer specialised training in certain areas that are directly related to rural economic activities and their natural features, including fishing, forestry, the environment, farming, etc. This training should meet the quality standards required to make specialist programmes a means of attracting learners, giving people who have done this training a relevant qualification and thus contributing to local socio-economic relaunch (EESC, 2016). Access to CVET is fundamental to developing self-employment and a competent workforce.

Lifelong learning is an umbrella term covering practically every aspect of finding knowledge and passing it on. It includes formal learning, such as via distance-learning media, and non-formal learning. It could be completely outside the education system (e.g. evening courses offered by local authorities, training delivered by professional and other associative bodies, and community-regeneration initiatives) or fully integrated into it.

Most micro- and small businesses need employees to be multi-skilled and flexible. Rather than being employed to do one specific job, employees work in small teams that collectively perform all the tasks needed to run the business. Employees in these businesses, therefore, have to perform tasks that in larger companies would be done by employees with several different job titles. This manner of operating is not always understood by city-centric educational institutions. Recognising the problem would help educators understand how micro- and small businesses operate and why the present 'job-focused' training and qualifications are not appropriate to how micro- and small businesses operate. This would also help small enterprises develop and support in-house work-based education and training (EESC, 2016).

European Council of Young Farmers (2017) stresses the need to promote new models of collaboration between generations of farmers through partnership; share-farming; long-term leasing and other long term arrangements; farm to farm arrangements, and land mobility services. Thus, young farmers are 'guardians' of the countryside and are eager to implement of innovative technology, science based research and farm management practices to guarantee a sustainable, profitable and productive future for farming (CEJA, 2017).

Young people considering entering farming are unlikely to simply follow traditional practices but will also experience individualisation in forming their own strategies for diversification, off-farm employment, or intensification. They will also require lifelong training, education and retraining, and appropriate institutional support. Shucksmith (2010) stresses importance of the extension and broadening of the New Entrants' Scheme. Zondag et al. (2015) also stress that it is not only important to adapt training programmes or other forms of knowledge transfer to the needs of farmers, especially young ones. It is equally important to know to whom the knowledge is being provided, as different types of farmers need different kinds of knowledge and learning methods.

The need to develop knowledge and skills, particularly entrepreneurial skills, in rural areas is of paramount importance. Concerning entrepreneurial skills, relatively little attention has been paid to the learning process leading to the development of these skills (Seuneke et al., 2013).

Zondag et al. (2015) argue that it is generally accepted that the development of entrepreneurship is important to enable socially responsible farming, as well as other strategic choices such as those related to the succession of the farm through diversification of the business and investment decisions. The specialisation of agriculture and forestry, and the particular challenges faced by micro-, small- and medium-sized enterprises in rural areas require an appropriate level of technical and economic training (Zondag et al., 2015). This training not only should comprise technological and managerial skills, but also entrepreneurial

skills, dividing the competences of farmers into three categories: craftsmanship, management and entrepreneurship. Craftsmanship relates to knowledge and experience on the technical level (regarding the product and the means of production), management relates to the arrangement and organisation of the production process, and entrepreneurship relates to strategic choices (Zondag et al., 2015). In the past, knowledge development often focused on craftsmanship and management, while much less attention was paid to entrepreneurship.

In the primary sector, rural entrepreneurs face a complex range of regulatory requirements, required by central, regional and local authorities (Deakins et al., 2016). These are related to animal and food safety, bio-security, environmental regulations, land use regulations and resource consents. Given that rural entrepreneurs, especially those in the primary sector, often have limited resources and networks compared to their urban counterparts, managing industry specific regulatory requirements can demand additional entrepreneurial skill for rural entrepreneurs in primary sector. Many formulations of entrepreneurial skill imply the presence of situational factors: markets, customers, investors or human resources, social networks and ties. But these situational factors become even more prevalent in a rural context (Deakins et al., 2016).

Euracademy Association (2009) stresses that individual knowledge of the locality – local practices in the landscape, local food, local habitation, local cultures and cultural practices, which are a key part of rural economic development now, and it is important that this distinctive local knowledge is not lost. Thus non-formal lifelong learning is increasingly important for rural development. Local knowledge, particularly traditional knowledge of useful practices, is an asset for community development, because the involvement of the community in the learning process is so important (Euracademy Association, 2009). Some knowledge belongs to individuals, some are collectively known and owned.

The EU's LEADER program is an example of such an endogenous place-based policy that has developed since the 1990s. The approach has received positive reviews in promoting rural development at local level. LEADER aims to stimulate rural development initiatives by helping rural associations, local authorities and rural action groups (LAGs) to devise innovative strategies for local development. The approach itself is primarily defined by 7 key principles, which are: area - based local development strategies, bottom-up elaboration and implementation of strategies, local public - private partnerships - LAGs, integrated and multi-sector actions, innovation, cooperation and networking (European Commission Regulation 1698/2005; European Commission regulation 1305/2013).

Despite the wide territorial spread and the use of the approach not only in rural development, but also in other policy instruments, the implementation of LEADER approach is assessed ambiguously, especially due to weak performance for LEADER added values, creating innovations and bureaucracy. (Courades & Brosei, 2018). In the future, LEADER will be seen as a tool that can help shape locally-based action and initiatives stemming from local needs. This would overcome the disregard for space-based needs and territorial diversity created by the space-blind approach. LEADER can be the basis for innovation, cooperation between territories, institutions and people, dissemination of new ideas.

Bosworth et al. (2016) conclude that in many LEADER groups, there was an understanding that innovations could emerge in many ways. Social innovations related issues are presented below (see subsection 4.8.1). In the Declaration of the Cork 2.0 Conference, it was stressed that stronger policy focus on social innovation, learning, education, advice and vocational training is essential for developing the skills in rural areas needed. This should be accompanied by the strengthening of networking and cooperation amongst farmers and rural entrepreneurs (European Commission, 2016a).

Findings demonstrate that both state-funded and private services for small-scale farmers are largely embedded in traditional, linear models of knowledge transfer. Accordingly, small-scale farmers have received formal advisory services. Utilising the state funding allocated to advisory services for small-scale farmers enables these farmers to access subsidies, otherwise important opportunities for innovation by both advisors and farmers can be lost.

Consequently, rural regions present enhanced opportunities for promoting the green transition and the reorientation of the local economy towards low-carbon development and innovative solutions to environmental concerns (ESPON, 2017). As an example – the application of circular economy principles to recycling agricultural waste; promotion of locally produced products supported by technology and ICT; and implementing, and taking full benefit of smart diversification in agri-food, energy, biomass, tourism and cultural activities etc. (ESPON, 2017). Enterprises within the circular bioeconomy can create business opportunities based on modern digital technologies and innovative business practices, as well as can make an important contribution to a more circular and resource-efficient economy in the EU's rural areas (EIP-AGRI, 2019). Therefore, to organise small and medium scale farmers through business planning, including developing the right business models, could be beneficial gaining those benefits that the sector can provide. Moreover, the bioeconomy will strengthen the bio-based sectors and develop new technologies to turn bio-waste into value, provide benefits to rural communities (European Commission, 2019b).

Limited knowledge about the possible uses and benefits of ICT creates difficulty for rural areas to attract and retain experienced workers due to a general lack of professionals, economies of scale for small business (OECD, 2018). Enhancing ICT skills and core digital competences should be among the priorities (European Commission, 2019b). The technology makes it possible to integrate the whole value chain; 3D printing, for example, opens up the possibility to produce locally and reduce the cost of prototyping new products and tools. It ultimately may reduce dependence of remote communities by bridging supply gaps for replacement and machine parts. OECD (2018) recommendations are as follows: (i) enhance knowledge about the technology's possibilities, put the basic infrastructure (internet, energy) in place and update local skills; (ii) necessity to value and develop more: creativity, flexibility, adaptability, collaboration, which should be built into early education; (iii) provide digital education/learning, which allows further teaching to be delivered in non-conventional ways; (iv) encourage vocational education (sharing examples of success), promote use of online courses and make use of rural assets in teaching. Besides, it is outlined that digital connectivity and new technologies will enable the collection and use of data that increases productivity and the delivery of better public services.

Milone and Ventura (2019) state that innovation is characteristic of a new generation of farmers, also called new peasant's generation, where innovation is a multidimensional, multi-level and multi-actor process. Besides, ICTs play a key role in the success of new peasant's generation. Small farms play an important role in the European countryside, providing employment, maintaining landscapes and nature, preserving both traditions and traditional products (EP, 2014). They also offer opportunities for new entrants to engage in innovative farm business development opportunities. New entrants or newcomers (i.e., neo-rural farmers) are innovators in their approach to collective and shared knowledge, responsibility for environment, and the look at the planet as an arena where social change takes place (Orria & Luise, 2017).

3.5 Ecosystem services

The section focuses on the explanation of the ecosystem services approach based on cultural and provisioning ecosystems, agroecosystems, capital approach, recreation and aesthetic landscapes contexts.

On EU level it is recognised that the vitality of ecosystems, including they inhabit and biodiversity, is the most important part of the manifold bioeconomy areas (European Commission, 2018). Moreover, EC stresses that healthy ecosystems are essential to human well-being.

Costanza et al. (2017) provide the definition of ecosystem services – 'Ecosystem services' (ES) are the ecological characteristics, functions, or processes that directly or indirectly contribute to human well-being: that is, the benefits that people derive from functioning ecosystems. It is important to distinguish between ecosystem processes and functions, on the one hand, and ecosystem services on the other. Ecosystem processes and functions contribute to ecosystem services, but they are not synonymous. Ecosystem processes and functions describe biophysical relationships that exist regardless of whether or not humans' benefit. By contrast, ecosystem services are those processes and functions that benefit people, consciously or unconsciously, directly or indirectly. However, the connections between ecosystem processes and functions and human well-being are complex and the various pathways are still not well understood, so we have to take a pluralistic and precautionary approach to assessing these connections and to the valuation of benefits (Costanza et al., 2017). Cultural and provisioning ecosystem services are most important for development of farming and rural economics.

Cultivated landscapes are landscapes in which cultural ecosystem services arise from the interaction between natural elements and processes and human activities (TEEB DE, 2016). Cultural ecosystem services are essential for developing a sense of place, recreation and tourism. These services cover a wealth of practices that contribute to regional identity, a sense of place, aesthetics and inspiration, as well as being a key location factor for economic development (TEEB DE, 2016). Cultural and provisioning ecosystem services and its benefits are reported in Table 5.

Ecosystem service	Benefits
Cultural	Recreation (i.e., eco-tourism & outdoor activities)
	Physical and experiential interactions
	Cultural (i.e., aesthetic, artistic, spiritual, education, & science)
	Aesthetic values and information
	Cultural diversity
	Knowledge systems
	Educational values
Provisioning	Food
	Fresh water
	Raw materials
	Fibre, etc.
	Genetic resources
	Biochemicals and natural medicines
	Medicinal resources
	Ornamental resources

Table 5 Cultural and provisioning ecosystem services and its benefits⁷

Jones et al. (2016) consider that both natural capital and human-derived (produced, human, social, cultural, financial) capital are necessary to create an ecosystem services at many levels. The impacts of agriculture are manifold. Whereas low intensity farming practices enhance biodiversity (i.e., high nature value farming) and provide a more balanced supply of ecosystem services, intensive agriculture has major impacts (mostly negative) on biodiversity, soil, water, air and climate. As a consequence, policy objectives in both the EU Biodiversity Strategy to 2020 and in the EC Communication outline ideas on the future of food and farming (European Commission, 2017), highlighting the need to enhance positive contribution of the agricultural sector to biodiversity and sustainable use of resources, including a reinforced commitment to the delivery of public goods and ecosystems services related to soil, water, biodiversity, air quality, climate action and the provision of landscape amenities.

Agroecosystems in good condition deliver benefits to everyone. From the farmer who needs healthy and fertile soils for growing crops to the consumers of agricultural products to the society at large through the supply of regulating and cultural services. Keeping agroecosystems in good condition requires “an agricultural policy with strong commitment to deliver public goods and ecosystems services related to soil, water, biodiversity, air quality, climate action and the provision of landscape amenities” (European Commission, 2017).

Species-based recreation and aesthetic landscapes are examples of cultural services. These show very different relationships between natural capital attributes and the service delivered (Smith et al., 2017). A review by Smith et al. (2017) supports the findings of IPBES by providing evidence of relationships between natural capital attributes and the service delivered, as well

⁷ Source: based on Costanza et al., 2017

as relationship among the conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity, long-term human well-being and sustainable development.

3.6 Multifunctionality of agriculture and farm diversification

Agricultural multifunctionality and farm diversification are two concepts that look at rural development from an agricultural perspective. They can be seen in many contexts. The section focuses on tourism, care farming and local food systems and short food chains. Multifunctionality as a set of rural attractiveness factors is related to sustainability, commodification, landscapes, non-commodity outputs, food, social networks, creative industries, social farming, civic agriculture, local food, and re-territorialisation as a policy are also analysed in this section.

A multifunctional countryside means that rural activity can obtain multiple results, not only with the production of goods and raw materials but also with value-added agro-food, tourism, and environmental and social benefits (Tulla et al., 2017). Agriculture can also contribute to the sustainability of the rural landscape, the protection of biodiversity, the creation of jobs along with the diversification of agro-industrial activities and services, and thus it contributes to the viability of rural areas. Tulla et al. (2017) argue that this new situation has been called ‘the commodification of the countryside’, in which consumers, who mainly live in cities, are prepared to pay more for the value of certain goods.

Multifunctionality and sustainability became guiding principles of agricultural policy since the late 1980s. The former refers to the fact that, beyond its primary function of supplying food and fibre, agriculture provides various benefits in the environmental and socio-economic realms. In addition, multifunctional agriculture has been propagated as a pathway to sustainable development (cf. Caron et al., 2008). This is based on an association of the various functions of agriculture to the social, economic and ecological dimensions of sustainable development. The concept of multifunctionality forms an essential basis for sustainable development strategies, though not yet fully exploited in all areas (EP, 2018).

The concept of landscape multifunctionality recognizes that rural landscapes have multiple functions in addition to agricultural and forestry commodity production (Fagerholm et al., 2019). Accordingly, multifunctional landscapes provide ecosystem services that are accessible to a broad range of beneficiaries. Moreover, there is strong evidence that people derive multiple benefits from ecosystems in multifunctional landscapes (Fagerholm et al., 2019). An overview of the various non-food multifunctional benefits from agriculture in relation to their relevance is presented in Table 6.

Benefit categories	Relevance for sustainable development
Environmental benefits	
Rural landscape	Impact on ecological capital
Biodiversity and habitats	
Ecosystem and watershed functions	
Water quality	
Gaseous emissions	
Soil quality	
Socio-economic and cultural benefits	
Food security	Economic capital, basic needs
Food safety	Public health; social capital
Animal welfare	Welfare of non-human beings
Rural employment	Economic stability, social capital
Viability of rural areas	Impact on social capital
Cultural heritage (i.e. historical buildings)	

Table 6 Relevance of multifunctional benefits from agriculture for sustainable development⁸

Non-commodity outputs (NCOs) contribute to rural GDP via direct channels (e.g. services) and other factors (e.g. the provision of landscape amenities) foster rural growth via indirect ones. NCOs affecting the rural standard of living directly contribute to rural economic performance in a straightforward manner. NCOs affecting regional welfare indirectly are not evident and can be identified only by evaluating the outcomes. From an economic perspective, direct links are the consequence of financial external effects, whereas most indirect links are the result of technological external effects (OECD, 2008).

Multifunctionality as a leading principle allows both to support agriculture and farmers in spite of the declining significance of agriculture as a productive space in rural areas, and to meet society's new demands for non-commodity outputs of agriculture and rural areas as a consumptive space (Molders, 2014). Therefore, multifunctionality can be conceptualised as variety of activities and functions for the farm and for the wider society. Such contributions include, inter alia, its role in food supply chains; its ability and potential to fulfil new societal goals; its contribution to rural employment and its role in the maintenance of rural population (McDonagh et al., 2009). Moreover, multifunctionality of agriculture and rural areas shows an impact on the economy, the environment, nature and also on societal and cultural development. The dimensions of multifunctionality deal with environmental, social and economic aspects (Fagioli et al., 2017).

A shrinking number of farmers manage to grow and/or intensify production. Many others cannot sustain themselves and have to part-time job to allow them to gain additional non-agricultural income. Finally, niche-production, diversification, multifunctionality, para-agriculture (i.e. activities which are not directly related to agriculture, such as renting out rooms and hosting workshops and banquets) and local food supply are ways in which small-scale farmers might survive (Lutz et al., 2017). All of these pathways benefit from cooperation, but it is particularly important for farmers endeavouring to set up local food supply systems. Cooperation is a practice historically well known to farmers. It occurs in a variety of situations, ranging from informal collaboration with relatives and neighbours at times of high workload (e.g. hay harvesting) to formal production, distribution and marketing cooperatives. As well

⁸ Source: based on Hediger & Knickel, 2009

as collaborating amongst themselves, farmers also cooperate with consumers and institutions (Lutz et al., 2017).

Farmers have increasingly started to join and shape so-called local, civic or alternative food networks. Often, these networks have been initiated by consumers, who want to establish a closer relationship between themselves and producers. Some have taken the form of food coops or solidarity purchasing groups, collectively purchasing directly from the farmers themselves. Other initiatives, such as Community Supported Agriculture (CSA), are characterised by a strong and enduring economic partnership between consumers and farmers (Lutz et al., 2017).

3.6.1 Tourism

Several scholars have adopted the concept of integrated rural tourism to refer exclusively to tourism related to the economic, cultural, environmental, and social development of rural areas. For example, it focuses on the strategic commercialization of resources and of place, and on the interplay between local and non-local forces in promoting sustainable development (Quaranta et al., 2016).

The diversification of farms into agritourism has grown considerably (Wright & Annes, 2014). Neumeier and Pollermann (2014) note that tourism can contribute to the creation of new job opportunities outside of agriculture and also strengthen the often declining small trade enterprises; as well as create positive economic impulses to entrepreneurship related to tourism.

There exist synergies between food production and rural tourism – the integration of local products into the local tourism experience as a strategic move to revitalise the local economy. Sustainable tourism and food systems are good examples of economic opportunities in rural areas, involving the protection and enhancement of cultural and natural heritage (European Commission, 2019b). Adding culinary elements to local tourism allows visitors to learn more about the cultural identity of a territory through its food. Culinary tourism creates new economic opportunities both for local producers and for the local area as a whole, without altering social, environmental, and cultural structures (Quaranta et al., 2016).

Formal and informal interactions between economic agents (e.g. farmers, artisan food producers, craftsmen) promote the complementarity of territorial resources, thereby allowing the rural tourism destination to offer an integrated product. The collective commitment of different actors in a network encourages new economic opportunities and the development of new strategies for rural tourism and is made stronger when the definition of network is extended to include the social interactions in a community and not only the ‘networks’ involved in economic exchange (Quaranta et al., 2016). Besides, social networks play an essential role in the economic and social development of rural tourism destinations. Moreover, the trust built between different members of a network allows for an exchange of knowledge and experience and the emergence of new ideas that can be turned into new strategies for development.

Creative industries and tourism are two of the most dynamic sectors in Europe’s post-industrial economy. The cultural heritage of monuments, museums, townscapes and

landscapes underpins the growth of jobs in these sectors (ESPON, 2006). Mottiar et al. (2018) consider that rural social entrepreneurs are a significant force in identifying the tourism potential in rural destinations (opportunists), catalysing a collective vision, and operating as network architects to achieve social objectives. While many peripheral rural areas face significant challenges in terms of sustaining communities and attracting tourists, it is often social entrepreneurs, as much as traditional entrepreneurs, who are involved in developing new ideas, new products and activities, and envisioning a future for the area (Mottiar et al. 2018).

Many rural areas have re-defined themselves as consumption spaces in which history and rural tradition take over from modern agricultural production as the key elements of identification (Richards, 2010). Another major influence on the nascent creative tourism market is the role of lifestyle entrepreneurs, who often tend to choose rural locations with established creative communities for their new enterprises. In rural areas, there have also been attempts to develop looser creative clusters based on concentrations of crafts producers and designers. Networks of crafts producers have been successful in developing a basis for cultural tourism (Richards, 2010).

3.6.2 Care farming

The transformations of agricultural sector from productivist towards multifunctional practices encourages changes within the health and social service sector from highly institutionalized to community care (de Krom & Dessein, 2013; Tulla et al., 2017). In this context, care-farming is the farm-based promotion of human health and social benefits (de Krom & Dessein, 2013). A wide range of new sustainable practices and activities in the sector of health care, social integration, rehabilitation of disadvantaged people, and training for those with specific needs are developed in rural regions. These practices and activities have different terms, such as 'social farming', 'care farming', 'farming for health', 'green care' or 'green therapy' (Scuderi et al., 2014; Meraner et al., 2015). In addition, the care farming or care farm has the following different interpretations: social farm, rehabilitation farm, residential farm, educational farm, community farm, therapeutic farm etc.

The care farming can be defined as the use of commercial farms and agricultural landscapes as a base for promoting mental and physical health, through normal farming activity; and to provide various other services, for example, educational, rehabilitation etc. (Hassink et al., 2013). Care farms offer care, supported workplaces and/or residential places for clients with a variety of disabilities (Hassink et al., 2013; Di Iacovo et al., 2014). Target groups include people with a mental illness, addiction, intellectual disabilities, older persons, children, problem youth, and long-term unemployed people (Hassink et al., 2013; Di Iacovo et al., 2014). The perceived benefits of care farms are improved physical, mental and social well-being.

Hassink et al. (2013) confirm that care farming can be seen as an innovative example of community-based services that can improve the quality of life. Krom and Dessein (2013), on the other hand, consider care farming as social innovation which meets social needs and strengthens civil society, and can promote cooperation between various local and regional actors.

Target groups include people with a mental illness, addiction, intellectual disabilities, older persons, children, problem youth, and long-term unemployed people (Hassink et al., 2013). The perceived benefits of care farms are improved physical, mental and social well-being. Meraner et al. (2015) provide evidence that care farming practices are defined more broadly and promote the rehabilitation of disadvantaged people, education and care and/or towards the integration of people with 'low contractual capacity', but there are also practices that support services in rural areas for specific target groups such as children and the elderly. Tulla et al. (2017) propose six various categories, which characterise social farming. The following categories are directly linked with activities and services provided: (i) activity, which includes agrarian products and their transformation, distribution and catering, rural services, and the attraction of nature and rural landscape environment; (ii) objectives, such as the integration of persons and groups at risk of social exclusion, achieving health benefits, or/and receiving income from having a job; and (iii) population, reflecting the diverse groups: people with mental, physical or psychological disability, social and economic integration difficulties and at risk of poverty (structural unemployment, drugs and other addictions, prisoners, immigrants, etc.), and young people with learning difficulties or older people with low income or social needs.

3.6.3 Local food systems and short food chains

Importance of SFCs and localized agri-food systems or LFSs has grown significantly in recent years (Bele et al., 2018). LFSs could help to preserve heritage and traditions; as well as provide opportunities to local communities and contribute to the generation of income and social cohesion through collective actions and activities (Bele et al., 2018). However, the European Commission (2013a) stresses that following definitions or descriptions used for the purpose of this report are used in research:

- 'local farming' means the production of agricultural products and foodstuffs with the aim of selling them in an area reasonably close to the farm of production;
- 'direct sales' means sales by a farmer directly to a consumer, without intermediaries on the selling side;
- 'short food supply chains' means sales from a farmer to a consumer with a reduced number of intermediaries.

Besides, the EC (2013a) encourages EU Member States to take a more proactive role: adapt legislation where possible for the particular benefit of small farmers and direct sales; take into account that food and catering are among priority sectors for green public procurement; provide local food to public canteens, public authorities; use innovative approaches to greening contracts while farmers, in order to be able to bid jointly in public procurement tenders; organise themselves and make use of various models of co-operation.

Recent decades have seen a re-birth of small-scale locally oriented food production. Consumer interest in local food and a growth in farmers markets and Community Supported Agriculture (CSA) programs have provided opportunity for community reintegration through agricultural practices (Obach & Tobin, 2014). Brunori et al. (2016) argue that at the consumer level, comparative sustainability assessment can promote more informed choices based on multiple criteria of economic, social, ethical, health and environmental impacts of food behaviour. The factors, which affect the local food systems, can consist by various socio-cultural and economic indicators (Mantino & Vanni, 2018).

Local and regional agri-food systems can occur through the ‘re-territorialisation’ or ‘re-localisation’ of the food supply chains or networks. The ‘re-localisation’ is constituted by: (i) value creation strategy – oriented to product differentiation along the dimensions of quality, locality and sustainability; (ii) supply chain (or supply network) organisational strategy – that aims to improve active clustering via strategic alliances, as well as creation of local clusters (Berti & Mulligan, 2016). The Committee of the Regions (2011), in its opinion on ‘Local food systems,’ confirms that the topic should be viewed in a broader context with: food and agriculture related to the EU 2020 Strategy; European agriculture model; and European objectives on agriculture. The Committee provides various benefits of local food systems (LFSs). Economic benefits of LFSs are as follows:

- LFSs support the local and regional economy by providing employment in agriculture and food production, including processing, distribution, marketing and sales activities and services
- when income is spent locally on locally produced food, it stays within the region and has a strong multiplier effect of the order of three on the regional income of the community compared with ordinary trade patterns;
- investing in local food systems would lead to economic recovery in underprivileged areas, better incomes for local producers, stronger cooperation between stakeholders, revived entrepreneurship, better openings to local markets, more employment, lower costs and maintenance of the local level of services and provisions;
- short distribution channels lead to greater interaction and mutual knowledge and understanding between consumers and producers;
- offering local products with authentic, traditional, original, sustainable, seasonal or other locally appreciated features supports social cohesion and community spirit and encourages the community to display environmentally friendly behaviour, etc.

Environmental benefits of LFSs are:

- LFSs bring environmental benefits through more sustainable production systems, reduced transport externalities (food miles) and opportunities to create circular systems based on organic waste, residues and renewable energy;
- every foodstuff has a ‘food miles’ count, leading to carbon emissions and resulting from transportation movements made between the local production area and the consumer. LFSs contribute to lowering the amount of food miles generated by a community;
- a local food product should preferably have a lower carbon footprint than an imported similar product. This footprint can be calculated by performing a Life Cycle Analysis on the product;
- producers are more likely to link unique selling points to consumers' expectations when they are operating in a local food system. These USPs may concern sustainable production circumstances, organic production or accompanying environmental services;
- the creation of local outlets for food products produced in very small quantities or with specific taste characteristics can help maintain biodiversity and promote the development of fruit and vegetable varieties and animal species in danger of disappearing;

- LFSs can nowadays be linked to circular economy systems and other regional challenges, such as organic waste management, water management, reuse of production residues, such as heat and renewable energy, etc.

LFS are associated with several benefits (i.e., high competitiveness), because their products are strongly linked to local assets (nature, know-how, and tradition). Besides, local culture, tradition, place, and origin-based quality are important in the creation of values, therefore localized food systems may contribute to preserve heritage and traditions (Bele et al., 2018). LFSs include cooperative forms into food hubs, local food networks, farmers' markets, CSAs, box schemes, buying clubs, and value chains, along with a range of agriculture and food cooperatives owned by farmers, consumers, workers, and in emerging multi stakeholder cooperative structures (Anderson et al., 2014). Several scholars have claimed that small-scale agriculture in which farmers sell goods to the local market has the potential to strengthen social ties and a sense of community, a phenomenon referred to as “civic agriculture.” Proponents see a lot of promise in the increase in the number of community supported agriculture (CSA) programs, farmers markets, and other locally orientated distribution systems as well as the growing interest among consumers for buying locally produced goods (Obach & Tobin, 2014).

Short Food Supply Chains (SFCs) have potential to improve farm incomes, promote sustainable farming systems and contribute to local economic development (EIP-AGRI, 2015). There are many different forms of SFCs in Europe, but they share a common characteristic of reduced numbers of intermediaries between the farmer or food producer, and the consumer. Whilst the number of SFCs has proliferated, their collective impact is limited by a number of barriers to scaling up. SFCs are collaborative activities in which more than one farmer, food producer, organisation or individual agree to work together to develop short food chains for mutual benefit. It identifies many benefits of collaboration including improved product range available to consumers; resource sharing amongst producers and processors; maintaining local food chain infrastructure (such as abattoirs); increased negotiating power for groups of producers; reduced competition between small producers, and mutual support to combat isolation and stress (EIP-AGRI, 2015).

The advantages of local food systems include fairer prices for farmers, fresh, local and seasonal produce for consumers, a reduced environmental impact, greater traceability and benefits for the local economy as well as community (Augere-Granier, 2016; Brunori et al., 2016). For example, local food systems create jobs in agriculture and food production, but they can also encourage tourism, bringing economic benefits to the region (Hendry et al., 2019). De Jong and Varley (2017) argue that over the last decade, increasing attention has been paid to the development of food tourism, because enjoying local food is recognized as an essential dimension of the tourist experience. Indeed, the current EU rural development policy 2014-2020 offers producers wishing to get involved in LFSs several incentives co-financed by the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (Augere-Granier, 2016).

3.7 Social aspects of rural areas

Social aspects in rural areas are important and can be viewed from different angles. The section highlights employment and job opportunities, women, young people, and new

entrants. They are analysed in different contexts - business fields, social networks and knowledge, investment, policy, out-migration, hurdles and adaptation.

European Institute for Gender Equality (2016) confirms that “...the situation of women and young people in rural areas remains precarious, often resulting in the out-migration of females and youngsters in economically active age groups. In some rural areas, the lack of training infrastructure and appropriate childcare facilities prevent entry or upskilling in the labour market.”

3.7.1 Employment and job opportunities

Kolvereid (2016) argues that rural location is significantly associated with a larger preference for self-employment, a stronger intention to start a business, an increased likelihood of being involved with business start-up efforts, and an increased rate of self-employment. People in rural areas, compared to people in urban and semi-urban areas, have stronger intentions to start a business and are more likely to be involved in new business start-up efforts, because they score higher on attitude (the preference for self-employment), subjective norm (knowing other entrepreneurs) and perceived behavioural control (confidence in skills) (Kolvereid, 2016). Providing people in rural areas with good framework conditions for entrepreneurship can be equally or even more important than providing job opportunities.

Social networks and trust appear to play an important role for small businesses, and social networks are especially important under new firm formation. Small farms play an important role in the European countryside, providing employment, maintaining landscapes and nature, preserving both traditions and traditional products (EP, 2014). They also offer opportunities for new entrants to engage in innovative farm business development opportunities. We argue for a re-balancing of support for small-scale farmers, so that advisors are incentivised to act as facilitators, and small-scale farmers themselves can become actively enrolled in AKIS as hybrid experts.

The specificity of LFSs is in the spatial features of the product, people, institutions and social relations that are embedded in food production. Social relationships relate to trust and cooperation among actors (Mantino & Vanni, 2018). Pindado and Sanchez (2017) evaluated differences that exist between new and established agri-entrepreneurs in 20 European countries, as well as differences in relation to their counterparts in non-agricultural ventures. The focus was on the analysis of resources and capabilities; entrepreneurial orientation (risk-taking, pro-activeness and innovativeness); and legitimation affecting the entrepreneurial process. Results suggest that agri-entrepreneurs have weaker entrepreneurial capabilities than those in other sectors. However, new entrants into the agricultural sector are not less entrepreneurial in relation to other sectors. Conversely, established agri-entrepreneurs are less proactive than other sectors. Findings show that new entrants into agriculture are more entrepreneurially oriented than established ones (Pindado & Sanchez, 2017).

Information and communication technology (ICT), digitalisation and knowledge-intensive activities are fundamental to the restructuring of rural regions in response to shrinkage. This includes new, smarter ways to harness ICT to more efficiently deliver public services and generate new employment opportunities (ESPON, 2017).

As new business opportunity that can be an important source of diversified and stable income for farmers and foresters—circular bioeconomy—for the creation of high-quality jobs, competitiveness and growth in rural areas (EIP-AGRI, 2019). In addition, the bioeconomy is an important contribution, which could be made to decarbonising economy while creating rural jobs (European Commission, 2019b). The creation of jobs, particularly in coastal and rural areas, should be provided through the growing participation of primary producers in their local bioeconomies (EC, 2018).

3.7.2 Women

The European Parliament (2018) concludes that many roles played by women in rural communities help to maintain vibrant rural areas and viable farm businesses. Despite their crucial contribution, rural women still face numerous challenges, such as difficulties accessing the labour market, a lack of adequate public services and a weak presence in decision-making forums. Rossi (2017) stresses that nevertheless some EU funding programmes include a gender (women) dimension, agricultural and rural development policies do not provide for specific measures for women in rural areas.

The gender gap caused by the unequal treatment of men and women as regards employment opportunities, job remuneration and participation in decision-making is wider in rural areas, where the degree of female participation in economic activities is lower, their levels of educational attainment are poorer and their risk of poverty and social exclusion is higher (EP, 2018). Furthermore, rural women often do not benefit from family-care support from public services. A gender gap is also evident in the agricultural sector, where women lack equal access to resources and specific training, and tend to manage smaller farms; the great majority of women in farming, meanwhile, are officially categorised as working on farms as ‘family members’, even when the daily routine of running the farm is shared equally with their partners.

Women can be at the forefront of innovation and diversification in rural areas by developing new activities, production lines and services (EIGE, 2016; EP, 2018). For example, women can develop agro-tourism activities, artisan food and drink production, craft enterprises, and telecommunication and caring services. Women often have the added advantage of an awareness and knowledge of local needs, and specific interpersonal and communication skills (EIGE, 2016).

European Parliament (2018) outlines the important role of women in rural areas, as well as their contribution to the farming sector, but it also emphasises the numerous challenges rural women face. It calls on the European Commission and Member States to act with appropriate measures, and using instruments available under EU policies, to create better living and working conditions for women in rural areas: by facilitating co-ownership of farm businesses, increasing women’s participation in representative bodies, disseminating information on funding opportunities, ensuring equitable access to land, and providing good quality public services. It is stated that women make significant contributions to the rural economy, and the diversification measures and the concept of multifunctionality, as an essential basis for sustainable development strategies, though not yet fully exploited in all areas, have opened up new opportunities for women, with the help of innovation and the creation of new concepts which make it possible to inject fresh dynamism into farming (EP, 2018).

Women are a driving force for the maintenance, conservation and development of rural areas, both in cultural and economic terms (EIGE, 2016). They contribute to the preservation of a rich and diversified cultural heritage and the transmission of traditions; and also represent a considerable proportion of the workforce in agriculture and contribute to the development of the rural sector in the face of constant depopulation. Unfortunately, women in rural areas are also an invisible force as their presence and role are not accurately reflected in statistics. Many of those who are involved in agricultural work do not receive a separate income from their husband or other male members of the household. By assisting their farmer husbands and other self-employed men, they are not entitled to social security in their own right and often do not hold property rights to land or farms (EIGE, 2016). To overcome this latter aspect, gender-sensitive initiatives such as shared ownership of farms and agricultural enterprises are being implemented in some European countries.

Wright and Annes (2014) recognise that some forms of rural tourism (i.e., agritourism) move women to the front stage of the farm unit. They argue that, for example, an educational or pedagogical farm tourism may provide a venue for recoding farm women as knowledgeable and authoritative. In addition, farm tourism allows women the chance to model professional expertise and transmit practical knowledge historically associated with men.

Women have a lower preference for self-employment than men, which can explain the low rate of self-employment among women (Kolvereid, 2016). Most of the young women who stayed in rural areas looked for employment in the public services, the traditional provider of female employment opportunities (Shucksmith, 2010). Young men thus appear often to have more freedom to shape their own biographies than young women, despite women's better educational qualifications. This, however, is not always the case. In relation to employment and social policy, there is a clear message for policies and delivery mechanisms to reflect and address social differentiation. Flexibility to suit each person's circumstances will be essential. This briefing note draws attention to a number of case studies, or models, which may offer some transferable ideas to practitioners in rural areas of Europe.

The research results in Sweden provided by Johansson (2016) show that net out-migration is only a reality in the ages between 18 and 24, while the opposite process has happened in the ages 25–29 and 30–34. This indicates that the 'problem' of out-migration of young women is an aspiration for education, and a tendency to get more women-friendly jobs. In the family creating ages, it seems to be a return-migration flow, with net in-migration as one consequence (Johansson, 2016).

3.7.3 Young people

Declining number – accordingly the share – of young people in rural areas is recognised in EU Member States, on EU level, as well as in all developed countries. One of the objectives of PoliRural is to find a way to improve the attractiveness of rural areas for young people through exchanges in innovative and inspiring practices and relevant policy tools and approaches.

The existence of a “young farmer problem” in Europe has been recognized by scientists and policy-makers and is based on the widespread acknowledgement of the poor generational renewal rates in the farming sector and in particular in farmland management across the EU

(Eistrup et al., 2019). Young farmers are environmentally conscious and are well-educated on current and future environmental and agricultural sustainability issues and challenges. At the forefront of their land management practices are environmental protection, biodiversity conservation and climate change mitigation (CEJA, 2017). Moreover, they want agriculture and agricultural landscapes to be recognised as public goods and they want not only to protect but also enhance the environment. Young farmers endeavour to sustain agricultural positive externalities that benefit civil society (such as protection of biodiversity, human health and well-being, food production, enhancing soil structure and fertility) and ensure the continuation of sustainable rural landscapes (CEJA, 2017).

Young farmers are also willing to introduce environmental measures at farm level, where the decisions to safeguard the environment e.g. through international climate change agreements, take place in practice. Furthermore, to achieve effective environmental policy that is all-encompassing and that acknowledges young farmers as the future of sustainable agriculture, young farmers are willing to engage with all stakeholders and policy and decision makers (CEJA, 2017). As new environmentalists, they accept the principle of increasing sustainably: environmental, social, economic.

The European Court of Auditors (ECA) (2017) notes that several EU documents, as well as EC statements, have stressed the high priority of supporting the young farmers and the generational renewal. The total EU budget allocated specifically for the support to young farmers over the 2007-2020 period is 9.6 billion euro. Nevertheless, the European Court of Auditors offers the general conclusion that the EU support for young farmers is based on a poorly-defined intervention logic, with no expected result and impact specified. It is also stressed that support should be better targeted to foster effective generational renewal.

Shucksmith (2010) considers that for many in rural communities one of the most pressing issues for the future sustainability of rural communities is the exodus of young people. Migration decisions of the youth are influenced by the geography of the locality, the social setting, the level of infrastructure, the provision of social services, the degree of accessibility, the condition of the local labour market and the role of family, friends and social networks. Shucksmith (2010) recommends that young people receive the following support: (i) better guidance from schools, careers services, and training and further education institutions, as well as local employment services; (ii) a greater emphasis in schools on developing active citizenship skills and nurturing an awareness and understanding of sustainable development; (iii) building an explicit youth element into rural community development, with facilitators employed to work specifically with young people, especially the least privileged; (iv) promoting a local culture, which accepts children and young people as social actors and as citizens to be included and valued.

3.7.4 Newcomers or new entrants

New entrants have different connotations. There are also different processes that affect why new entrants go to the countryside or stay in the countryside and engage in agriculture or other business. The processes of new entrance is influenced by urban-rural relations (urban-rural migration), changes of ownership in agriculture itself (inherited property, new farms), rural areas as a place of business (new business models). The subsection analyses new rural entrants (newcomers), entrants in farming and successors.

Newcomers in rural areas and in-migration process to rural areas in academic literature are characterised under various terms and definitions. Counter urbanisation is a demographic and social process whereby people move from urban areas to rural areas (Halfacree, 2008). This selectivity clearly indicates a selective rural renaissance. Halfacree (2008) proposed that 'back-to-the-land' counter urbanisation is associated with efforts to produce new forms of land-related places which link community with land, nature, food, etc.

Eimermann (2015), studying lifestyle migration and counter urbanisation, suggests that lifestyle migration could be understood as "...spatial mobility of relatively affluent individuals of all ages, moving either part-time or full-time to places that are meaningful because, for various reasons, they offer the potential of a better quality of life". Movement of new entrants to farming is widely recognised as crucial to the ongoing vitality and competitiveness of the agricultural sector and rural regions in Europe (Sutherland, 2015).

In the earlier stages of EIP-AGRI focus group, "New entrants into farming" – the working definition of a new entrants to farming – was proposed by Sutherland (2015): "A natural person, group of people or legal entity who have within the past five years established a new agricultural holding or farming business in their own name(s). The natural person, group of people or legal entity should be actively farming (i.e. producing agricultural products for sale) and be either establishing a new agricultural holding or returning to a family-held holding after a minimum of 10 years of off-farm employment."

However, in the final report (EIP-AGRI, 2016) the focus group concluded that suitable definitions needed to be developed to reflect the purpose of the associated activities. For instance, if the purpose is to engage young people, then an age limit may be appropriate. If the purpose is to enable innovation and diversification on farms, then the nature of the intended activity, rather than the characteristics of the individual or household, is most important. Experts of focus group note that the support needs of potential new entrants – across the spectrum of possible types – are thus highly variable.

New entrants are defined in the NEWBIE network (2018) "...as anyone who starts a new farm business or becomes involved in an existing farm business. They comprise a wide range of ages, agricultural experience and resource access. Newcomers and successors can enter farming at any stage in their working lives". They face common barriers: access to land, labour, capital, housing, labour, markets, business skills, knowledge and the networks needed to acquire these resources (Helms et al., 2018, Lorleberg et al., 2015; Dessen et al., 2013; Sutherland, 2015; EIP-AGRI, 2016). Controversially, Scoones (2009) concludes that urban-to-rural migrants may benefit from access to natural resources, being able to transform these benefits into human capital.

Entry models by Helms et al. (2018) are defined as approaches, methods and/or instruments, which can help to overcome resource access barriers for new entrants in farming. These can be e.g. new forms of farm co-operation between landowners and new entrepreneurs like partnerships including junior-senior-partnerships, contract farming, share farming, or land access with support by an incubator institution.

NEWBIE studies' results in participant countries confirm that 'new entrants' business models are primarily belonging to (or are a mixture of): (i) differentiation (niche products and markets: organic farming, short chains, direct sale); (ii) Alternative Food Networks (Community Supported Agriculture, co-production), and (iii) on-farm diversification (pedagogical, social, recreation) (Helms et al., 2018).

Milone and Venture (2019) argue that new peasant farms are more resilient to the on-going challenges of climate change and globalisation as the young new peasants have a high capacity for adaptation. Their entrepreneurship is based not only on conventional skills and knowledge learned in business and agricultural schools, but on their 'social instinct' which allows them to be creative and innovative in managing the unknown and surviving adversity and challenges. Sutherland et al. (2017) report that small farms offer opportunities for new entrants to engage in innovative farm business development. Moreover, they recognise that new entrants in particular are expected to bring with them new ideas and skills which can be operationalised on their farms.

New entrants or newcomers (i.e. neo-rural farmers) adopting a more radical approach develop forms of innovation and cooperation between producers and consumers, which in effect are bottom-up practices leading to active social innovation (Orria & Luise, 2017). Orria and Luise (2017) use the name 'neo-rurals' for migrants from urban to rural areas who attempt to achieve a predominantly agrarian lifestyle. Authors note that in academic literature they have been presented as: 'neo-farmers', 'neo-peasants', 'new pioneers', new agrarians and back-to-the-landers.

Orria and Luise (2017) confirm that their findings are in line with Bock (2012) highlighting correspondence between social innovation practices and rural social innovation process. Madureira et al. (2015) also found that younger new entrants were particularly adept at using ICT on their farms, particularly for advertising the farm business and diversification activities e.g. advertising their bed and breakfasts (Maureira et al., 2015). Pinto-Correia et al. (2015) identified access to ICT (e.g., high speed broadband) as an important factor in the decision to relocate to a lifestyle property. In her cases, ICT was not specifically identified as important to business development; instead, ICT represented part of an amenity lifestyle and enabled remote working.

PoliRural uses a broad definition of new entrants to better reflect the dynamics of rural economies and the actors that enrich the lives and increase the sustainability of those who live there. So, new entrants that we're interested in are really the new entrants to rural economy, not just farming, particular, tourism and leisure, energy, manufacturing, carbon farming and circular economy activities which share their supply chains with urban areas. PoliRural accepts new behavioural trends (e.g. telecommuting, co-ops, entrepreneurs seeking lower rents) which could have an impact on the structure of working and living in rural areas or new institutional actors that may have a transformational effect on rural society and economy, good or bad, for instance, buy-up distressed assets on behalf of the big-food, energy and tourism players. Although the latter are important, they don't represent the full complexity of rural life. Moreover, the sustainability and long term success of new entrants to farming will rely on the richness, variety and success of other economic factors needed to support them directly and indirectly.

3.8 Social innovations and innovative activities

Social innovation and innovative activities are important in rural development. This section looks at social innovation in relation to social enterprises, corporate social responsibility and crowdfunding.

3.8.1 Social innovations and social enterprise

Caulier-Grice et al. (2012) state that the term social innovation has been used broadly to describe: (i) societal transformation; (ii) a model of organisational management; (iii) social entrepreneurship; (iv) development of new products, services and programmes; (v) a model of governance, empowerment and capacity building. Distinction between social and economic innovation is impractical and restrictive because there are many cases of social innovations, which are also economic innovations e.g. the fair trade and microfinance movements. Caulier-Grice et al. (2012) stress that social innovations can include new types of production and new markets for social or environmental goods; moreover, it can include employment, consumption or participation, but it can include ownership and production e.g. co-operatives or community owned wind farms.

Caulier-Grice et al. (2012) define social innovations as “... are new solutions (products, services, models, markets, processes etc.) that simultaneously meet a social need (more effectively than existing solutions) and lead to new or improved capabilities and relationships and better use of assets and resources. In other words, social innovations are both good for society and enhance society’s capacity to act.”

It should be noted that the European Commission’s (2013b) definition is similar to the definition proposed by Caulier-Grice and co-authors: “Social innovation can be defined as the development and implementation of new ideas (products, services and models) to meet social needs and create new social relationships or collaborations. It represents new responses to pressing social demands, which affect the process of social interactions. It is aimed at improving human well-being. Social innovations are innovations that are social in both their ends and their means. They are innovations that are not only good for society but also enhance individuals’ capacity to act.”

Pisano et al. (2015) consider that social innovations respond to the multiple social, economic and environmental issues. They can be defined as new solutions (products, services, models, markets, processes, etc.) that simultaneously meet a social need (more effectively than existing solutions) and lead to new or improved capabilities and relationships and better use of assets and resources. Pisano et al. (2015) argue that the social innovation can occur as a product, production process, or technology, but also as a principle, an idea, a piece of legislation, a social movement, an intervention, or some combination of them. Because social innovations are context dependent, it is happening in the broader social, cultural, economic and environmental contexts.

Nowadays, social innovations, particularly in the rural areas, focus on successful solution to different social, economic, political and environmental issues. The social benefits could be, for example reducing the threat of climate change (reduction of greenhouse gas emissions); maintaining the biodiversity, ecosystems (agroecosystems; forest ecosystems) and

landscapes; offering fresh and healthy local food etc., which could be provided by the social innovations based on the agricultural production and other rural activities (Kirwan et al., 2013).

Bock (2016) points out that successful social innovations are supposed to result from collective action and creative social learning and address unmet social needs. In the rural context, this includes needs such as income and employment, health care and other public services. The need for society to innovate is underlined by the purpose of creating a better society with more equality, social inclusion and social justice (Bock, 2016). It concerns the need for rural society to ensure its resilience in the light of changes in society at large and changing rural-urban relationships. Social innovation as defined above refers to changes in rural societies that are pertinent to their survival, particularly social relations, available capabilities, readiness to engage the collective and the capacity to organise collective action (Bock, 2016). Besides, it is expected to deliver more radical innovations, for example functionality of products, novel business and delivery models; collaboration etc., as well as improvement self-efficacy and self-reliance of residents in general.

Bock (2016) also considers that social innovations aims to fulfil the needs of rural residents through the provision of (or alternatives for) services that are no longer available. The need to reorganise and reinvent local service provision promotes the establishment of novel forms of collaboration among residents, businesses, including farms, NGOs and local governance. There is a new role for co-operatives and collective actions with self-determination, self-management and self-reliance. The initiatives are driven by an intrinsic motivation to improve the quality of life in the community and the currently offered services.

Orria and Luise (2017) confirm that their findings are in line with Bock (2012) highlighting correspondence between social innovation practices and rural social innovation process. Three main interpretations of social innovation are distinguished: (1) social mechanisms; (2) social responsibility; and (3) innovation of society. Besides, Orria and Luise (2017) stress the high importance of neo-rural farmers in developing a rural social innovation business model. Social capital, particularly well-developed social networks, in rural areas play an important role for small businesses formation (Kolvereid, 2016).

Neumeier (2017) provides two characteristics of social innovation which (1) always produces or enhances social capital and focuses not only on needs but also on asset building; (2) has two dimensions: a process dimension (e.g. mobilising actors, participation process), and an outcome dimension (e.g. new and improved means of collaborative action, new governance structures) (Neumeier, 2017). This understanding of social innovation implies that empowerment and learning are both sources and outcomes of well-being (Neumeier, 2017). Furthermore, not every process of social learning, networking or collaboration necessarily results in a social innovation.

The European Commission (2019a) emphasises support for the development of social enterprises, because they focus on achieving wider social, environmental or community objectives and prioritise their social impact over profit. Besides, they are managed in an open and responsible manner, and involve employees, consumers and stakeholders affected by their commercial activities.

Social entrepreneurs in rural areas, more than others, support rural development (Mottiar et al., 2018). Moreover, they are more active than traditional entrepreneurs, and are involved in developing new ideas, new products and activities, and in envisioning a future for the area. It is accepted that social entrepreneurship is “an innovative, social value-creating activity that can occur within or across the non-profit, business or government sector” (Mottiar et al., 2018).

3.8.2 Corporate social responsibility

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) was defined in the CSR Strategy as the “the responsibility of enterprises for their impacts on society” (European Commission, 2019c). To fully meet their social responsibility, companies “should have in place a process to integrate social, environmental, ethical, human rights and consumer concerns into their business operations and core strategy in close collaboration with their stakeholders, with the aim of maximising the creation of shared value for their owners/shareholders and civil society at large and identifying, preventing and mitigating possible adverse impacts.”

In turn, the term ‘CSR disclosure’ is similar to the other terms, e.g. ‘social and environmental disclosure’ and ‘corporate social reporting’. CSR disclosure is a voluntary provision of information on a corporation’s interaction with its natural and social environment (Ali et al., 2018). Engert et al. (2016) point out that the CSR can be achieved at the crossroads of economic development, environmental protection and social responsibility. Consequently, managing corporate sustainability is ‘a strategic and profit-driven corporate response to environmental and social issues caused through the organisation’s primary and secondary activities’ (Engert et al., 2016). European Commission (2019c) points out that key actions to encouraging socially- and environmentally-friendly business practices are:

- Sustainable public procurement rules;
- European Pillar of Social Rights;
- Promoting social entrepreneurship and social innovation;
- An EU Action Plan for the circular economy;
- Supporting the sustainability of agriculture; fisheries and aquaculture; forestry, logging and timber;
- Promoting market uptake through labelling.

Corporate social responsibility reporting, the disclosure of social and environmental information in annual reports and on websites, is gaining in popularity; and is mostly voluntary (De Villiers & Marques, 2016). Consumer criticism of agricultural activity and agribusiness has been increasing due to growing ecological awareness, echoing an increasing understanding of how agriculture activity is irresponsible from the social and ecological perspectives (Dahlsrud, 2008). Certainly, CSR concept provides the basis for evaluating the social performance of agriculture and the agri-food chains as a whole (Hediger, 2013). It is proposed to complement multifunctionality and sustainability, and to contribute to a more enlightened agricultural and food policy debate (Dahlsrud, 2008; Hediger, 2013). Hartman (2011) points out that as far as CSR can serve as a safeguard against following risks: a food safety, animal welfare, environmental incidence, social responsibility, a reputation, it may be especially important for agri-food enterprises.

To build sustainable agriculture that is socially responsible, the focus should be on the core entities in the CAP. Mazur-Wierzbicka (2015) considers that the concept of CSR could play a crucial role in meeting new economic, social and environmental challenges of sustainable agriculture. Therefore, farms could be able to meet the requirements of their stakeholders (i.e. consumers, public institutions etc.) related to the natural environment, as well as make decisions in compliance with the CSR standards.

3.8.3 Crowdfunding

Crowdfunding – “generally refers to open calls to the wider public to raise funds for a specific project. Often these calls are published and promoted through the internet and with the help of social media and are open only for a specified time period. The funds are raised from a larger number of contributors with relatively small contributions, but exceptions exist” (European Commission, 2014). It utilises the power of the crowd in contributing information and solving problems (Hosseini et al., 2015). There is great potential in crowdfunding to complement traditional sources of finance and contribute to the financing of the real economy. The Green Paper on Long Term Financing of the European Economy initiated a broad debate on the different factors that enable the European economy to channel funding towards the long-term investments needed to ensure economic growth (European Commission, 2014).

The priority areas where the EC intends to take initiatives are to help SMEs attract funding. Crowdfunding is part of this work plan. It is one of the newly emerging financing models that increasingly contributes to helping start-ups move up the ‘funding escalator’ and contributes to building a pluralistic and resilient social market economy. Furthermore, crowdfunding has real potential to finance different types of projects, such as innovative, creative and cultural projects, or activities of social entrepreneurs, that have difficulties in accessing other forms of financing (European Commission, 2014).

European Commission (2014) points out that the expression ‘crowdfunding’ refers merely to a channel of financing, which can be used in many different ways. Donations can be collected from people, which would qualify as donation-based crowdfunding if collected for a specific project during a specified time period promoted through internet and social media. But crowdfunding campaigns can also offer contributors something in exchange. One can talk about rewards-based or pre-sales crowdfunding when contributors get in return something symbolic, like the opportunity to participate in the cultural experience they finance (e.g. appearing as an extra in a film), or a product that was developed and produced with the funds raised. All of the above forms of crowdfunding can be described as ‘crowd sponsoring’.

In turn, crowdsourcing uses social engagement techniques to help a group of people achieve a shared, usually significant, and large goal by working collaboratively together as a group. Crowdsourcing also usually entails a greater level of effort, time and intellectual input from an individual than just socially engaging (Holly, 2010).

Crowdsourcing implies voluntary participation of individuals, with no hierarchy or contract related constraint, as well as a high degree of autonomy in the achievement of tasks. A typology of crowdsourcing practices is based on two criteria: the integrative or selective nature of the process and the type of tasks that are crowdsourced (Brabham, 2008). Besides, Holley (2010) argues that most of the crowdsourcing sites had either no paid staff or very

limited staffing, because they manage two things: (1) utilised volunteers to moderate/coordinate other volunteers and to answer the questions of other volunteers; and (2) implemented IT through open source software. Crowdsourcing during crisis relies on different types of motivation for participation than other forms of crowdsourcing, especially the micro-payment incentive structure on sites. The motivation for participation on crisis-related crowdsourcing platforms is imbedded in the social needs of individuals to help in the face of tragedy (Starbird, 2011).

The differences between crowdfunding and crowdsourcing could be indicated as follows. Crowdfunding involves outsourcing the financing of a project to the general public. Its intention is to limit the use of professional investors; and starts with announcements designed to raise awareness of the projects seeking supporters. The majority of crowd funders are private individuals, who may not know each other and who choose freely — how much they want to invest, the projects they wish to invest in, the industries they are interested in. Crowdsourcing is the technique of outsourcing specific tasks to external participants. The participants typically learn about assignments by a request via a platform on the Internet. This opens up the ability to obtain services with immediate access, cheaper/cost efficient, more relevant one off usage, problem solving approach.

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3.9 Conclusions of the literature review

The literature review highlights the orientation towards agriculture as a view of the main occupation of the rural population. In this context, rural development is linked to the retention of young people in the countryside and new entrants to the countryside, which is crucial for future rural development. The demands of young people and new entrants for certain services overlap with the concept of quality of life, which includes both physical, social, economic and

financial conditions, which are not always favorable for further development. Crowdsourcing is one example of how to deal with financing issues.

In addition to traditional occupations, rural areas are supplemented by industries that complement farms or are completely unrelated to agriculture. However, the use of natural capital in a non-traditional way is essential for rural development, which opens the door to the multifunctionality and diversification of rural business. Tourism, the production and sale of local food, short food chains, social entrepreneurship, collaborative care farms, the local community, socially responsible action, and smart governance are some examples of the direction that should be developed.

Ecosystem services are a complex concept that links culture, provisioning and agrarian practices to the rural landscape as a place to live and farm. The interconnections of agroecosystems open up a view on the possibilities of developing new approaches based on the bioeconomy, the circular economy, and the landscape itself as a service.

A critical factor is the knowledge and skills that must be both locally oriented (local knowledge) and innovation that is brought in from outside. Social innovations form the basis of farming rooted in a certain place. It is not always valued and used. It is important to have a variety of knowledge that can help to build a business in different areas, not just one particular specialization. Lifelong learning, professional knowledge, non-formal education, together with social contacts form the basis for knowledge transfer and sustainability of skills in a given area.

In addition to the economic attractiveness of rural areas, social factors are important: social equality, women's equality and their role in rural development, employment and business balance are important aspects that must be taken into account when analysing needs and formulating territorial policies.

And finally, the attractiveness of the countryside is rooted in the territory - a certain place on which it semantically depends. Local capital, as a set of advantages and assets, is formed from the set of features of each territory, manifested in the needs of people. The attractiveness of rural areas has a subjectivity in the cultural context, which requires a special attitude from rural policy makers.

4 Creation of preliminary vision's definition of rural attractiveness

4.1 PoliRural partners' workshop – brainstorming

The schedule and activities of the PoliRural consortium partner workshop (June 20, 2019, Prague) are presented in Figure 8.

Introduction 5"	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Moderator explains aim of the workshop – brainstorming mechanics
Group work 'A': mapping exercise 20"	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Participants are split into 4 groups •Group discussions
Group work 'A' presentations 20"	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •A rapporteur from each group delivers a short presentation •Answers to a) b) c) from all groups are displayed on master canvas •Four definitions are pinned on whiteboard/flip chart
Brief discussion ensues	
Group work 'B': testing the definitions from different perspectives 20"	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Each group now works with someone else's definition, not their own •Definition is tested by viewing it from the perspective of different stakeholders •Each group can have ~3 personas/companies as stakeholders without overlap •Rapporteur from each groups delivers a short presentation
Group work 'B': presentations 25"	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Moderator records the answers underneath each definition on whiteboard/flip chart
Brief discussion ensues	

Figure 8 Workshop schedule, activities and description

The PoliRural partners have been divided into four groups. Each group took part in a brainstorming session, and groups' work description – aims and tasks – are reported in Table 7.

Activity	Aim and task
Group work 'A': mapping exercise	The aim is to set the context for future discussion by capturing general trends, developments etc.
	Task 1: discuss as a team and record on post-its: a) rural assets, b) rural needs and challenges, c) rural opportunities and enablers
	Task 2: based on the above, propose a definition of rural attractiveness (3-5 sentences) e.g. rural attractiveness is...
Group work 'B': testing the definitions from different perspectives	The aim is to paint a more nuanced picture of rural attractiveness
	Task: working as a team, assess the definition of rural attractiveness from the perspective of your personas/companies – is it complete? What is missing? What could be added, if anything?

Table 7 Groups' work description

The photos below provide insight into the meeting (Figure 9 and Figure 10).

Figure 9 Introduction to the workshop – brainstorming by moderator Pavel Kogut

Figure 10 Workshop discussions before brainstorming session among PoliRural partners

Conducting the group work ‘B’ – testing the vision’s definition of rural attractiveness, different hypothetical stakeholders have been used. These stakeholders can be various personas/companies, who intend or wish to:

- start farming, i.e., to agriculture related business;
- start non-agricultural rural business;
- diversify farming activities, providing service connected with tourism;
- be self-employed or look for rural job, etc.

The stakeholders present various social groups of rural residents or newcomers (i.e., residents, new entrants, young people women, etc.). Description/characteristics of hypothetical personas/companies for testing vision's definition are presented in Table 8.

Company/enterprise (i.e., farm)/ employer, self-employer, job seeker	YP	NE	PNE	W
Laura, a young adult with a city/finance background looking to start an agri-tech business	X		X	X
Agneta, the wife of a small-plantation owner who now needs to look after a newborn baby and is therefore afraid she may not be able help on the farm as much as she would like to	X			X
Pedro, a self-employed web designer living in a rural area		X		
Anton, a smallholder with 30 years of farming experience who would like to diversify his income, with his wife, by renting out a lodge to tourists				
Anna, 23, who studying veterinary science at a university, received two internship offers – one from a city based clinic, another from a rural clinic – not sure which one to take	X		X	X
Juris and his wife want to go back to Latvia and a beekeeping business, having previously worked in a UK honey factory			X	
Nikos, an experienced data scientist looking for job opportunities in any sector so long as he can use his knowledge and skills				
Irini, 35, lives in a capital and has no farming experience, but is keen to grow some vegetables on the roof of her house after she read an article about urban agriculture	X			X
SEASONAL Ltd, an employment agency in fruit picking business that connects British farmers with Eastern European labour force			X	
MEATY Ltd, an importer of British meat into the EU, now fears the business may be severely affected by hard Brexit, e.g. tariff barriers, customs, extra veterinary checks etc.			X	
Francois, 15, is in his final year at local high-school and still undecided about future career path	X			
Johanis, a 29-year-old urban worker who has just inherited some urban land from his deceased parents	X		X	
Omar, a refugee from Sudan who used to sell vegetables back home and now would like to set up a similar business in Europe			X	

YP – young people; NE – new entrants; PNE – potential new entrants; W – women

Table 8 Description/characteristics of hypothetical stakeholders

Identification and recording were done using post-its, on which participants had to record a) rural assets, b) rural needs and challenges, c) rural opportunities and enablers. Individual thoughts were discussed and summarized in the group (Figure 11). The results of brainstorming were presented by the representative of each group (Figure 12).

Figure 11 Group discussion in the brainstorming session, Group work 'A'

Figure 12 Presentation of results of Group work 'A'

4.2 Results of PoliRural partners' workshop – brainstorming

4.2.1 Group work 'A' results

The aim of Group work 'A' – mapping exercise – is to set the context for future discussion by capturing general trends, developments etc., with related tasks:

- Task 1 – to discuss as a team and record on post-its: a) rural assets, b) rural needs and challenges, c) rural opportunities and enablers;
- Task 2 is, based on the above, to propose a definition of rural attractiveness (3–5 sentences), e.g., rural attractiveness is "...".

The identification of items related to the particular asset was done in line with possible assets (Figure 13).

Figure 13 Rural assets for group work

The compiled and summarized results of group work ‘A’ first task – identification and recording with post-its: a) rural assets, b) rural needs and challenges, c) rural opportunities and enablers, are reported in Annex 1 (Table 17). As an example, the post-its of two groups are shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14 Results of Group work ‘A’ presented by two groups

The second task of group work 'A' – to create and define the vision of rural attractiveness – has been discussed and presented by each group; results are included in Annex 1 (Table 17).

4.2.2 Group work 'B' results

In this step, an overall aim of Group work 'B' is to paint a more nuanced picture of rural attractiveness. In this context, each group working as a team must assess the definition of rural attractiveness from the perspective of hypothetical stakeholders – given personas/companies. Is it complete? What is missing? What could be added, if anything? Results of vision's definition which have been tested from the perspective of various stakeholders (hypothetical personas/companies) are presented in the Table 9.

Enterprise (i.e., farm)/ employer, self-employer	Assessment of vision's definition	
	Missing items	Main needs
Laura, a young adult with a city/finance background looking to start an agri-tech business		Education & training Business support
Agneta, the wife of a small-plantation owner who now needs to look after a newborn baby and is therefore afraid she may not be able help on the farm as much as she would like to	Definition of quality services	Childcare
Pedro, a self-employed web designer living in a rural area	Jobs for young people	Broadband required Rural attractiveness
Anton, a smallholder with 30 years of farming experience who would like to diversify his income, with his wife, by renting out a lodge to tourists	Local economy	Infrastructure, esp. roads and high speed internet
Anna, 23, who studying veterinary science at a university, received two internship offers – one from a city based clinic, another from a rural clinic – not sure which one to take		Infrastructure Public services
Juris and his wife want to go back to Latvia and a beekeeping business, having previously worked in a UK honey factory	Local economy	Education & training

Nikos, an experienced data scientist looking for job opportunities in any sector so long as he can use his knowledge and skills		Infrastructure (i.e., high speed internet)
Irini, 35, lives in a capital and has no farming experience, but is keen to grow some vegetables on the roof of her house after she read an article about urban agriculture		Education & training
SEASONAL Ltd, an employment agency in fruit picking business that connects British farmers with Eastern European labour force		Not relevant
MEATY Ltd, an importer of British meat into the EU, now fears the business may be severely affected by hard Brexit, e.g. tariff barriers, customs, extra veterinary checks etc.		Infrastructure New entrant's support Advisory service
Francois, 15, is in his final year at local high-school and still undecided about future career path		
Johanis, a 29-year-old urban worker who has just inherited some urban land from his diseased parents		Public services (esp. health care, social service etc.)
Omar, a refugee from Sudan who used to sell vegetables back home and now would like to set up a similar business in Europe		Religious services Business support

Table 9 Vision's definition testing results from the perspective of hypothetical stakeholders

Source: results of brainstorming's group work B

5 Results of PoliRural partners' questionnaire survey

Questionnaires (see Annex 2) to PoliRural partners were sent by email and filled questionnaires were submitted in the same way. Reporting data from the questionnaire were compiled, summarized and analysed. Results are presented in two sections; the first applies to prioritization of rural attractiveness vision's definition, but the second to the specification of rural assets, needs and challenges, and opportunities and enablers.

5.1 Prioritization of rural attractiveness vision's definition

Submitted data of respondents are presented in Annex 3 (Table 19). The data have been compiled and summarized, and average value or mean value of each vision's definition of rural attractiveness was calculated. The Table 10 shows the results of analysis of submitted data regarding prioritization of vision's definition of rural attractiveness. Besides, for each vision's definition the numbers of first priority and second priority were calculated and added at the end of the table. First priority is marked in green and bold, but second priority in black and bold (Table 10). Results of vision's definition prioritization by PoliRural partners are shown in Figure 15.

Figure 15 Average priority value of vision's definition⁹

In order to evaluate the priority of each rural attractiveness vision's definition, it is necessary to look at a set of different averages, since the results of the survey are influenced by the interests, subjective opinions and the specific time of the respondents. As described above (see section 2), descriptive statistics were calculated. Its results are presented in Table 11. As can be concluded from the average values for each vision's definition's priority, it is similar for all measures except definition number five. This indicates that fifth definition should be recognised as a primary one. This is also illustrated by the mode and median values of descriptive statistics (Table 11). The second priority has been given to the second definition, which has the second lowest mean value. The dispersion is also small, and the estimate coincides with the calculated mode value. The third priority could be given to the sixth definition, ranked by the vast majority of respondents. Concerning the first definition, there is the greatest difference of definitions' priorities evaluation. The highest frequency indicates that first definition should be on fifth place (mode value), but 7 respondents (20%) also stress it as a fourth priority. This indicates that the respondents' choice in this case was determined by somewhat additional circumstances. Therefore, we can consider that this first definition

⁹ Source: based on questionnaire survey's reporting data (n=30)

could be the fifth priority, and third definition could be as fourth priority, but definition number four could be ranked on sixth place.

Consortium partner		Vision's definition					
		1	2	3	4	5	6
No. ¹⁰	Abbreviation	Priority					
1	CULS	5	2	3	6	1	4
2	CCSS	4	1	3	5	2	6
3	PLAN4ALL	5	2	4	1	6	6
4	NUVIT	5	2	1	4	3	6
5	SPU v Nitre	5	2	3	6	1	4
6	Agroinstitut	5	3	4	6	1	2
7	CityNitra	4	3	5	6	1	2
9	OZ VIPA SK	5	3	2	1	4	6
11	VPR	4	3	2	1	6	5
12	AREI	1	5	6	2	3	4
13	LLF	6	3	5	2	1	4
14	NP	3	6	4	5	2	1
15	GAIA	2	4	1	5	3	6
17	PSTE	5	1	3	6	2	4
19	MIGAL	1	2	2	4	3	3
20	21C CONSULTANCY	3	2	4	6	1	5
21	INNOVAGR	1	2	3	3	1	3
24	JIIP (VC)	6	3	4	5	1	2
24	JIIP (FZ)	3	4	6	5	2	1
25	VITO	1	2	4	6	3	1
26	AgFutura	2	4	6	1	5	3
27	CoO	1	3	3	2	2	1
28	TRAGSA	5	2	3	4	1	6
29	SocialInnolabs	3	6	4	5	2	1
30	22SISTEMA	1	2	6	5	3	4
31	S&L	6	4	2	1	5	3
32	HAMK	2	5	4	6	3	1
34	MAC (GC)	1	6	4	2	5	3
34	MAC (JO)	6	5	4	1	2	3
37	GGP	1	4	6	2	5	3
Priority, average		3.40	3.20	3.70	3.80	2.67	3.43
Vision's definition, no of 1st priority		8	2	2	6	9	6
Vision's definition, no of 2nd priority		2	10	4	5	7	3

Table 10 Results of vision's definition prioritization by PoliRural partners¹¹

¹⁰ No of partner in PoliRural Grant Agreement and Consortia Agreement

¹¹ Source: based on questionnaire survey's reporting data (n=30)

Value name	Vision's definition					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
Mean	3.40	3.20	3.70	3.80	2.67	3.43
SD	1.87	1.45	1.44	1.97	1.6	1.76
Mode	5.00	2.00	4.00	6.00	1.00	3.00
Median	3.50	3.00	4.00	4.50	2.00	3.00
Priority of vision's definition	5	2	4	6	1	3

Table 11 Results of descriptive statistics¹²

Rural attractiveness vision's definitions ranked by priority are presented in Table 12.

No.	Vision's definition	Priority
5	Rural attractiveness is sustainable rural communities with access to high quality public services, a thriving and diverse local economy where agriculture related activities are complemented by sustainable tourism and other forms of employment in a working countryside, and an attractive, ecologically rich and accessible countryside in which the environment and biodiversity are conserved and enhanced ¹³	1
2	Rural attractiveness is about a place where everyone wants to live, enjoys high-quality services, proper infrastructure and community spirit, where jobs and living opportunities abound, and where one can find healthy and resilient environment ¹⁴	2
6	Rural attractiveness is vibrant, inclusive and sustainable rural communities, supported by diversified rural economies and by effective stewardship of high-quality environment and cultural heritage ¹⁵	3
3	Rural attractiveness is about providing good overall quality of life, freedom to express oneself, employment opportunities, and easy access to a city, good quality services and food. It is a place surrounded by landscapes ²	4
1	Rural attractiveness means rural areas make effective use of rural assets to improve an overall well-being and build strong and sustainable communities ²	5
4	Rural attractiveness is a nice place to live and work, to achieve social, economic and environmental potential ²	6

Table 12 Vision's definition of rural attractiveness, results of prioritization¹⁶

5.2 Rural attractiveness assets, needs and challenges, and opportunities and enablers

PoliRural partners evaluated items of rural attractiveness assets, as well as items of needs and challenges, and enablers and opportunities of rural areas.

Respondents have accepted or rejected items included in the questionnaire of survey Annex 2). Items are identified by groups during workshop – brainstorming. Several items were added or supplemented later, and their inclusion was based on literature review.

The reported data by respondents are presented in Annex 3 (Table 19).

¹² Source: own calculations, based on reporting data

¹³ Scott, A. J., Shorten, J., Owen, R., Owen, I. (2011). What kind of countryside do the public want: community visions from Wales UK?. *GeoJournal*, 76(4), 417-436.

¹⁴ Created during kick-off meeting's workshop – brainstorming

¹⁵ European Rural Parliament (2015). European Rural Manifesto. <http://www.europeanruralparliament.com>

¹⁶ Source: own calculations, based on reporting data.

Compiled results of reporting data of rural attractiveness' assets, needs and challenges, and opportunities and enablers are presented accordingly in Table 13, Table 14 and Table 15.

Public goods	Biodiversity
	Ecosystem services
	Cultural heritage
	Preserving and maintaining monuments (characteristic buildings, farms, churches etc.)
	Agriculture adapted to needs of landscape/ nature preservation
	Landscapes/ nature
Recreation	Ecological tourism; agri-tourism
	On-farm diversification (educational, social, recreation, health/ care)
	Care farming
	Ecologically sustainable tourism
	Place for leisure
	Fishing, sailing, hiking/walking, etc.
Identity	Sense of belonging
	Enhance personality
	Integrating new arrivals to the community
	Being part of a group with common ideas
Natural capital	Un-renewable natural resource land
	Land ownership & use benefits
	Natural resources, including water (natural watersheds)
Individual well-being	Freedom
	Tranquillity
	Contentment
	Proximity to nature
	High quality and healthy food (agricultural/ food products)
Human capital	Problem solving skills
	Willing to help
	Human centred design
	Energetic, talented & diligent people
	Community spirit
	Appropriate skill mix to exploit new rural reality
	Bottom-up development
Living conditions	Cheaper property
	Accommodation availability
	Pleasant and high quality environment
	Alternation of landscapes
	Quality of life
	Clean & fresh air
Good water quality (watersheds)	

Table 13 Rural attractiveness assets¹⁷

¹⁷ Source: based on questionnaire survey's reporting data

Demographic	Outflow of young people (to urban areas: education, jobs)
	Need to attract new young people to area
	Highlighting local opportunities & quality of life advantages
	Difficult to enter established farming community
	Population aging & the young / children
	Marriage / partners
Environment & Nature/ biodiversity	Climate change
	Natural disasters
	Nature conservation
	New types of pollution (water, air, soil)
	Biodiversity enhancement
	Ecosystem services
	Ecosystem awareness
	Nature / natural habitat
	Soil quality / preservation
	Support and advice on ways of farming
	Good solid waste management and waste water treatment
Innovation	Digitisation
	Social innovation
	Sharing economy
	Energy – wind, solar, hydro energy
	People and community driven
	People and community centred
Economy	New, high-income jobs
	Diversifying the farm business (e.g. into agri-tourism, cultural tourism, landscaping, social or green care, education, etc.)
	Support for entrepreneurs/ start-ups
	Income generating capacity at large (beyond farming)
	Short & local food chains – selling products at the farm (organic products, special products, such as cheeses, etc.)
	Encourage short supply chains – linking consumers to suppliers
	Producing value-added products and services that are differentiated from conventional products and supply chains (i.e., niche marketing)
	Bioeconomy & circular economy (valorisation of by-products & side products, agricultural, food and forest waste and raw materials)
Service provision	Lack of access to public services (e.g. good health care services, schools, kindergartens, etc.)
	Infrastructure in general (i.e., routes and road access, public transport, etc.)
	Improving access to internet and communications technologies
	Traditional services: groceries/bakeries disappearing, mobility services, municipality services at greater distance
	Community services (e.g. meeting places, local advice, agri-tourist information points, etc.)
	Affordable health services in reach (medical doctors, small health centres nearby, pharmacies, etc.)

	For elderly people to commute – mobility and transport (bus services, local voluntary transport services, e.g. small busses, cheap rural taxis, etc.)
Social	Poverty and social exclusion
	Skill shortage / relevance
	Lack of qualified professionals; experienced & traditional knowledge transfer
	Lack of social and community supports
	Loneliness (esp. for elderly people with limited capacity to move around)
	Civic participation and engagement
	Making the countryside more attractive for other people than the local residents (e.g. new entrants).
Need to develop broad range of skillsets in rural areas for bioeconomy & circular economy, renewable energy, tourism.	
Business (i.e., farming)	Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) or social and environmental disclosures

Table 14 Needs & challenges¹⁸

Social	Place for retirement
	Social inclusion or integration & third age innovation
	Sustainable and resilient community
	Availability of services (often included in the infrastructure factor)
	Easy & affordable mobility
	Seasonal workers
	Social innovations
	Social enterprises
Agriculture	Demand for local/organic food
	Multifunctionality of agriculture
	Diversification of farming activities
	Support for small and family farmers
	Simple rules for direct sale from the farms (e.g. short supply chain)
	Organic farming
	Alternative Food Networks, Community Supported Agriculture (CSA)
	Niche products (goods and services)
	Producing value-added products and services that are differentiated from conventional products and supply chains (i.e., short supply chains, niche marketing, branded products).
	Production other agricultural products; re-introducing other varieties (older species, new-to-the area products)
	Responsible and precise farming
	Use of biofertilizers
	Environmentally sound cultivation practices
Valorisation and management of by-products & side products, agricultural, food and forest waste and raw materials	
Abandoned houses	

¹⁸ Source: based on questionnaire survey's reporting data

Housing	Energy and other resources effective housing
	Affordability of housing
	Low cost of living
	High quality sustainable designed-for-all housing options
	Low rents / cheap(er) housing prices
	Accommodation availability
	Revitalize old houses
Economy	Short & local supply chain
	More young people establish SMEs
	Sustainable tourism
	Developing a share economy
	Crowd-funding & crowdsourcing
	Rural services (e.g., care farming, high value added food products, agri-food tourism, leisure activities)
	Freshwater aquaculture
	Incubator-supported start-up
	Cooperatives with specific characteristics (e.g., women cooperative businesses or producing a differential products or services)
	Business models, which have been successful to date
	Co-production & Co-design
	Resource efficiency & sustainability
	Bioeconomy & Circular economy
Renewable energy (e.g. wind and solar energy)	

Table 15 Opportunities & enablers¹⁹

Evidence has shown the classic ‘top-down’ model of rural development to be ineffective at driving rural development and fails to recognise the considerable potential for growth in rural areas. Consequently, there has been a new focus on alternative ‘bottom-up’ development models. The challenge is to design policy (i.e., measures), which address the social well-being needs of rural inhabitants (i.e., farm households), rural businesses and communities more broadly, in ways which do not unnecessarily inhibit the efficiency of the industry (e.g., agriculture, forestry, tourism, etc.). However, economic, environmental and social dimensions of development are interlinked, the needs of rural people are not directly influenced by their performance. Besides, various socio-demographic groups are presented by residents, which have both common and different needs.

Recognising that sustainable development in rural areas, in which an economic growth and performance is indisputable basis or fundament for well-being of rural people, including provision of high quality of life, it could be possible to vision/define the attractiveness of rural places in shorter form, as follows (Table 16); more to people needs oriented.

Attractiveness of rural area	a place where people want to live because conditions are created for the well-being of people of all ages
	vibrant, inclusive and sustainable rural communities

¹⁹ Source: based on questionnaire survey’s reporting data

	a nice place to live and work, to achieve social, economic and environmental potential
	better place in which to live and work
	provides high quality of life and well-being for those living in them
	vibrant, inclusive and sustainable rural communities that contribute to an equitable and just society
	provide a high quality life to all rural inhabitants
	a place where people from different population groups want to live and work, to achieve their social, economic and environmental potential
	enables people to stay in or relocate to rural areas, and avoids the need for people to leave rural areas involuntarily
	a viable, healthy and pleasant place to live, work and visit
	vibrant, inclusive, sustainable rural communities that provide a high quality life to all socio-demographic groups
	a place where people want to live and for quality of life are created good conditions

Table 16 Vision of rural attractiveness

6 Conclusions

This deliverable 1.1 of the PoliRural project has presented an initial vision (vision's definition) of rural attractiveness. It is recognised that no single definition exists for rural attractiveness. Moreover, rural attractiveness is practically not defined, but instead limits itself to descriptions and explanations from various authors. Rural attractiveness is more linked with competitiveness of territories, attractiveness investment, as well as development of tourism. It is largely related to landscapes, their quality and attractiveness. It is generally recognised that territorial capital is a crucial dimension of the attractiveness of places. Therefore, views on it differ, and there also are different factors that constitute attractiveness. Factors and indicators constituting attractiveness are based on territorial capital (i.e. environmental, anthropic, economic, social-cultural, human and institutional capital) and assets. Their choice and assessment can depend on size of territory (state, region, municipality), and on target/stakeholder groups. It can be, for instance, a sector, (e.g. public, NGOs, governmental), field (e.g. agriculture, tourism, forestry, ITC), various socio-demographic groups (inhabitants, new entrants/newcomers, visitors, etc.; age, gender, prosperity and health state, etc.), human, including education level.

The difficulties arising from multiple interpretation are also captured in the differing views of the PoliRural participants. As a result of the PoliRural participants' brainstorming, survey and literature review, the initial vision of rural attractiveness was developed and offered for further improvement; in particular its definition, which received highest assessment. It is possible that during the progress of the project implementation, the second most appropriate definition might become more adequate.

Up to now, in (rural) attractiveness research, more attention was paid to the environmental, economic and human factors. Socio-demographic factors were analysed by assessing trends of population's changes, employment, living conditions, prosperity etc. Less attention was paid to the important phenomenon and description of particular stakeholders' (i.e. socio-demographic groups) rural attractiveness. Further progress in sustainable rural development is possible, using the complete environmental, economic (e.g. financial), social and human as well as cultural potential. Their mutual interaction plays a significant role, for instance, in the creation and maintenance of landscapes. In order to secure rural development, the economic growth is necessary, and it should be ensured by development of business and creation of income, also for the rural municipalities that provide or foster availability of public services for the rural residents.

Regarding "new rural paradigm", possibilities are opening up in rural territories: diversify farming activities, based on multifunctionality of agriculture, to develop new various non-agricultural businesses. These could be products and services, and oriented to local, national or international customers. Innovations, including social innovations, and development of knowledge and skills via education, continuing vocational education and training (i.e. lifelong learning), are key factors affecting quality of employees. Mastering entrepreneurial skills is especially important. Socio-demographic groups are important for rural development: new entrants/ new comers, young people (especially well-educated ones), women, including young ones, creative people etc. Therefore, it is necessary to find out the characteristics of attractiveness for these groups, including the important factors/indicators.

7 Acknowledgements

This Deliverable has been prepared with the assistance of the PoliRural project partners, providing feedback (questionnaire survey) on initial rural attractiveness vision's definition. Special thanks to Pavel Kogut for framing and conducting the workshop – brainstorming for PoliRural partners.

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9 Annex 1 Results of workshop – brainstorming

The results of group work 'A' (Table 17 below).

Assets

Public goods	Biodiversity
	(Cultural) heritage
	Landscapes
Recreation	Ecological tourism
	Place for leisure
Identity	Sense of belonging
Natural capital	Land
	Natural resources
Individual well-being	Freedom
	Tranquillity
	Proximity to nature
	High quality food
Human capital	Problem solving skills
	Energetic, talented but hard-nosed people
	Community spirit
Living conditions	Cheaper property
	Pleasant environment
	Quality of life
	Good water quality (watersheds)

Needs & challenges

Demographic	Outflow of young people
	Population aging
	Marriage/partners
Environment	Climate change
	Natural disasters
	New types of pollution
Innovation	Digitisation
	Sharing economy
Economy	New (high-income) jobs
	Quality of employment
Service provision	Lack of access
Social	Skill shortage / relevance
	Lack of qualified professionals
	Loneliness
	VET ²⁰
Business	Socially responsible companies

²⁰ VET – vocational education and training

Opportunities & enablers

Social	Place for retirement
	Seasonal workers
	Wealthy bachelors
	Low cost of living
	New skills brought by migrants
Agriculture	Demand for local/ organic food
	Organic farming
Housing	Abandoned houses
	Two-place living (city-rural)
	Low rents
Economy	Short supply chains
	More young people establish SMEs
	Tourism

Table 17 Assets, needs and challenges, and opportunities and enablers created by groups

The results of the second part of group work 'A' – creation of vision's definition of rural attractiveness are presented in Table 18.

No.	Vision / Definition	
1	Rural attractiveness	means rural areas make effective use of rural assets to improve an overall well-being and build strong and sustainable communities
2	Rural attractiveness	is about a place where everyone wants to live, enjoy high-quality services, proper infrastructure and community spirit, where jobs and living opportunities abound, and where one can find healthy and resilient environment
3	Rural attractiveness	is about providing good overall quality of life, freedom to express oneself, employment opportunities, easy access to a city, good quality services and food. It is a place surrounded by landscapes
4	Rural attractiveness	is a nice place to live and work, to achieve social, economic and environmental potential

Table 18 Vision's definition of rural attractiveness created by groups

10 Annex 2 Questionnaire for survey

Questionnaire

1. Please, prioritize visions / definitions of rural attractiveness, indicating each of them with a number.

In your opinion, more appropriate or more suitable vision could be indicated as first – 1, less suitable last – 6.

If you are not satisfied with the definitions provided, create your own by compiling them.

No.	Vision / Definition		Priority
1	Rural attractiveness	means rural areas make effective use of rural assets to improve an overall well-being and build strong and sustainable communities ²¹	
2	Rural attractiveness	is about a place where everyone wants to live, enjoy high-quality services, proper infrastructure and community spirit, where jobs and living opportunities abound, and where one can find healthy and resilient environment ¹	
3	Rural attractiveness	is about providing good overall quality of life, freedom to express oneself, employment opportunities, easy access to a city, good quality services and food. It is a place surrounded by landscapes ¹	
4	Rural attractiveness	is a nice place to live and work, to achieve social, economic and environmental potential ¹	
5	Rural attractiveness	is sustainable rural communities with access to high quality public services, a thriving and diverse local economy where agriculture related activities are complemented by sustainable tourism and other forms of employment in a working countryside, and an attractive, ecologically rich and accessible countryside in which the environment and biodiversity are conserved and enhanced ²²	
6	Rural attractiveness	is vibrant, inclusive and sustainable rural communities, supported by diversified rural economies and by effective stewardship of high-quality environment and cultural heritage ²³	

Your proposed vision / definition

²¹ Created during kick-off meeting's workshop – brainstorming

²² Scott, A. J., Shorten, J., Owen, R., & Owen, I. (2011). What kind of countryside do the public want: community visions from Wales UK? *GeoJournal*, 76(4), 417-436.

²³ European Rural Parliament (2015). European Rural Manifesto. <http://www.europeanruralparliament.com>

2. Please indicate with “x”, if you agree to supplement with proposed items. If you would like to add or delete some items, use track changes or comments.

Assets

Public goods	Biodiversity
	Ecosystem services
	Cultural heritage
	Preserving and maintaining monuments (characteristic buildings, farms, churches etc.)
	Agriculture adapted to needs of landscape/ nature preservation
	Landscapes/ nature
Recreation	Ecological tourism; agri-tourism
	On-farm diversification (educational, social, recreation, health/ care)
	Care farming ²⁴
	Ecologically sustainable tourism
	Place for leisure
	Fishing, sailing, hiking/walking, etc.
Identity	Sense of belonging
	Enhance personality
	Integrating new arrivals to the community
	Being part of a group with common ideas
Natural capital	Un-renewable natural resource land
	Land ownership & use benefits
	Natural resources, including water (natural watersheds)
Individual well-being	Freedom
	Tranquillity
	Contentment
	Proximity to nature
	High quality and healthy food (agricultural/ food products)
Human capital	Problem solving skills
	Willing to help
	Human centred design
	Energetic, talented & diligent people
	Community spirit
	Appropriate skill mix to exploit new rural reality
	Bottom-up development
Living conditions	Cheaper property
	Accommodation availability
	Pleasant and high quality environment
	Alternation of landscapes
	Quality of life
	Clean & fresh air
	Good water quality (watersheds)

²⁴ Care farming – farming practices aiming at promoting the rehabilitation of disadvantaged people, education and care and/or towards the integration of people with ‘low contractual capacity’, but also practices that support services in rural areas for specific target groups such as children and the elderly (Meraner et al., 2015).

Needs and challenges

Demographic	Outflow of young people (to urban areas: education, jobs)
	Need to attract new young people to area
	Highlighting local opportunities & quality of life advantages
	Difficult to enter established farming community
	Population aging & the young / children
	Marriage / partners
Environment & Nature/ biodiversity	Climate change
	Natural disasters
	Nature conservation
	New types of pollution (water, air, soil)
	Biodiversity enhancement
	Ecosystem services
	Ecosystem awareness
	Nature / natural habitat
	Soil quality / preservation
	Support and advice on ways of farming
	Good solid waste management and wastewater treatment
Innovation	Digitisation
	Social innovation
	Sharing economy
	Energy – wind, solar, hydro energy
	People and community driven
	People and community centred
Economy	New, high-income jobs
	Diversifying the farm business (e.g. into agri-tourism, cultural tourism, landscaping, social or green care, education, etc.)
	Support for entrepreneurs/ start-ups
	Income generating capacity at large (beyond farming)
	Short & local food chains – selling products at the farm (organic products, special products, such as cheeses, etc.)
	Encourage short supply chains – linking consumers to suppliers
	Producing value-added products and services that are differentiated from conventional products and supply chains (i.e., niche marketing)
	Bioeconomy & circular economy (valorisation of by-products & side products, agricultural, food and forest waste and raw materials)
Service provision	Lack of access to public services (e.g. good health care services, schools, kindergartens, etc.)
	Infrastructure in general (i.e., routes and road access, public transport, etc.)
	Improving access to internet and communications technologies
	Traditional services: groceries/bakeries disappearing, mobility services, municipality services at greater distance
	Community services (e.g. meeting places, local advice, agri-tourist information points, etc.)
	Affordable health services in reach (medical doctors, small health centres nearby, pharmacies, etc.)

	For elderly people to commute – mobility and transport (bus services, local voluntary transport services, e.g. small busses, cheap rural taxis, etc.)
Social	Poverty and social exclusion
	Skill shortage / relevance
	Lack of qualified professionals; experienced & traditional knowledge transfer
	Lack of social and community supports
	Loneliness (esp. for elderly people with limited capacity to move around)
	Civic participation and engagement
	Making the countryside more attractive for other people than the local residents (e.g. new entrants).
	Need to develop broad range of skillsets in rural areas for bioeconomy & circular economy, renewable energy, tourism.
Business (i.e., farming)	Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) ²⁵ or social and environmental disclosures ²⁶

Opportunities and enablers

Social	Place for retirement
	Social inclusion or integration & third age innovation
	Sustainable and resilient community
	Availability of services (often included in the infrastructure factor)
	Easy & affordable mobility
	Seasonal workers
	Social innovations ²⁷
	Social enterprises ²⁸
Agriculture	Demand for local/organic food
	Multifunctionality of agriculture ²⁹
	Diversification of farming activities
	Support for small and family farmers
	Simple rules for direct sale from the farms (e.g. short supply chain)

²⁵ CSR – “the responsibility of enterprises for their impacts on society”. CSR enterprises should have a process to integrate social, environmental, ethical, human rights. Consumer concerns into their business operations and core strategy in close collaboration with their stakeholders, aimed to maximising the creation of shared value for their owners/shareholders, and for other stakeholders, society at large; identifying, preventing and mitigating their possible adverse impacts (EC, 2011).

²⁶ ‘CSR disclosure’ is similar to the other terms, e.g., ‘social and environmental disclosure’ and ‘corporate social reporting’. CSR disclosure – voluntary provision of information on a corporation’s interaction with its natural and social environment (Ali et al., 2018).

²⁷ Social innovation – the development and implementation of new ideas (products, services and models) to meet social needs and create new social relationships or collaborations. It represents new responses to pressing social demands, which affect the process of social interactions. It is aimed at improving human well-being. Social innovations are innovations that are social in both their ends and their means. It is not good only for society but also enhance individuals’ capacity to act. (EC, 2013).

²⁸ “Social entrepreneurship – aimed to solve community based problems, can play an important role as well in addressing sustainability challenges, while fostering inclusive growth and job creation locally, shared prosperity, and social inclusion” (EC, 2019).

²⁹ Multifunctionality of agriculture may be “...existence of multiple commodity and non-commodity outputs that are jointly produced by agriculture” (Van der Ploeg & Marsden, 2008); multifunctionality is variety of activities and functions for the farm and for the wider society (McDonagh et al., 2009).

	Organic farming
	Alternative Food Networks, Community Supported Agriculture (CSA)
	Niche products (goods and services)
	Producing value-added products and services that are differentiated from conventional products and supply chains (i.e., short supply chains, niche marketing, branded products).
	Production other agricultural products; re-introducing other varieties (older species, new-to-the area products)
	Responsible and precise farming
	Use of biofertilizers
	Environmentally sound cultivation practices
	Valorisation and management of by-products & side products, agricultural, food and forest waste and raw materials
Housing	Abandoned houses
	Energy and other resources effective housing
	Affordability of housing
	Low cost of living
	High quality sustainable designed-for-all housing options
	Low rents / cheap(er) housing prices
	Accommodation availability
	Revitalize old houses
Economy	Short & local supply chain
	More young people establish SMEs
	Sustainable tourism
	Developing a share economy
	Crowd-funding ³⁰ & crowdsourcing
	Rural services (e.g., care farming, high value added food products, agri-food tourism, leisure activities)
	Freshwater aquaculture
	Incubator-supported start-up
	Cooperatives with specific characteristics (e.g., women cooperative businesses or producing a differential products or services)
	Business models, which have been successful to date
	Co-production & Co-design
	Resource efficiency ³¹ & sustainability
	Bioeconomy ³² & Circular economy ³³

³⁰ Crowdfunding – “refers to open calls to the wider public to raise funds for a specific project. Often these calls are published and promoted through the internet and with the help of social media. The funds are raised from a larger number of contributors with relatively small contributions, but exceptions exist” (EC, 2014). It utilises the power of the crowd in contributing information and solving problems (Hosseini et al., 2015).

³¹ “Resource efficiency: is a way to deliver more with less. It increases aggregate economic value through more productive use of resources over their life cycle, i.e., minimising impacts of one resource's use on other resources, including the environment” (EC, 2011).

³² “...the production of renewable biological resources and the conversion of these resources and waste streams into value added products, such as food, feed, bio-based products and bioenergy” (EC, 2012). “Sustainable bioeconomy for Europe: strengthening the connection between economy, society and the environment” (EC, 2019).

³³ “Circular economy, where the value of products, materials and resources is maintained for as long as possible, and the generation of waste and pollution minimised” (EC, 2019); and “...waste and resource use are minimised, and resources are kept within the economy when a product has reached the end of its life, to be used again and

	Renewable energy (e.g. wind and solar energy)
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again to create further value” (EC, 2015). In a circular economy the value of products and materials is maintained for as long as possible; waste and resource use are minimised, and resources are kept within the economy when a product has reached the end of its life, to be used again and again to create further value.

11 Annex 3 Reporting results of PoliRural partners' questionnaire survey

This Annex presents reporting results of PoliRural partners' survey questionnaire.

No.	Partner	Vision's definition proposed
3	P4A	I think, that we need to do this as simple as possible
4	NUVIT	Rural attractiveness: A place where people want to live because conditions are created for the well-being of people of all ages. A place where people want to live and for quality of life are created good conditions (such as the availability of quality education and health care, environment, job opportunities, the community place where they can rest, etc.).
5	SUA	Would be nice to add its way of life; healthy lifestyle without a stress of the city in which family lives in symbiosis with a nature; attractive life choice especially for young generation,
7	CityNitra	I would propose to add it is a place where family values are accepted and supported by the community
19	MIGAL	The Galilee in Israel, although far from the centre, is an agricultural rural area that has the best environmental and cultural heritage but is lacking economic opportunities.
21	Innovagritech	Quality of services, possibility of work also through the activation of tools for teleworking. Community spirit and access to transport infrastructures (airports, train stations, etc.).
24	JiIP VC	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Rural attractiveness is about providing good overall quality of life, freedom to express oneself, employment opportunities, easy access to a city, good quality services, environment and food. It is a place surrounded by landscapes, with the implementation of a bioeconomy concept to guarantee the sustainability of rural community and its biodiversity. 2. Rural attractiveness is about sustainable rural communities with access to: high quality public services; high quality sustainable designed-for-all housing options; a thriving and diverse local economy where agriculture related activities are complemented by sustainable tourism and other forms of employment in a working countryside, promoting the traditional skills and sustainable agriculture and food production, and the traditional lifestyle, and a result also the built environment; an attractive, ecologically rich and accessible countryside in which the environment and biodiversity are conserved and enhanced.
27	CoO	Our future depends on valuation of ecologic values as to compare "beauty" with billions, ecology – based on "beauty" against \$, ecology will lose! As expert at the court, often winner, based on damages from economy against ecology due to economy damages ecology valuation, we have new balance models on technology and know-how like ecology-, 2 regional integrative-, 3 cross-border balance that in show-case, model exists, should be integrated! Interested parties please contact!
34	MAC GC	Rural attractiveness is a viable, healthy and pleasant place to live, work and visit.
34	MAC JO	A place where people from different population groups want to live and work, to achieve their social, economic and environmental potential.

Table 19 Proposed vision's definition by some PoliRural partners

Source: based on questionnaire survey's reporting data

12 Annex 4 Responses to the monitors' comments

Comments made by the monitors	Explanation
<p>Overall: This deliverable raises interesting points around the diversity of rural areas, the importance of natural assets, the desire to create places where people want to live and work and the need to be attentive to sustainability. The report is quite chaotic and poorly structured overall, it does not provide a smooth synthesis of the literature and jumps around quite a lot. For instance lifestyle migration is introduced in a few sections of the review.</p>	<p>The revised version structured in more detail and more clearly. Text formatted throughout the report. Text added in the introduction, and explained the purpose of each chapter Literature review - removed duplicates, and corrected text explanation and Figure 3 added, short explanation on each section added. A new section Conclusions of literature review added.</p>
<p>Another major problem is the lack of clarification of core concepts. Core concepts for the ongoing work need to be clarified. This will help to solve the fragmentation of the project's tasks and will provide the basis for its scientific coordination. For instance, rural is understood in a very basic way in which the 'rural' is understood - there are many different types of rural - P.19 - offers one version of the 'rural' - of depopulation etc. But rural is differentiated and some rural areas do not suffer from population decline (especially relevant to those areas that are not remote). Further on p. 20 the reference to cheap housing in rural areas is not necessarily the case for very desirable rural communities that one might find in Belgium or parts of Germany for instance. The OECD has published quite a lot of work on the classification of rural areas.</p>	<p>Rural concept clarified in the revised version. A new section 3.1 with core concepts added. Text added on different rurality added in section 3.1 and 3.3.</p>
<p>The report focuses on rural attractiveness but does address the 'attractiveness of farming' or 'farming attractiveness' (as referred to in GA, page 12). Since the H2020 sister project focus on farming and the CAP in particular, PoliRural's aim to cover the attractiveness of rural areas in general is convincing. PoliRural will focus on regional development in rural areas. State of the art relating to this orientation and delineation, including reference to the widely available scientific literature is needed. For example: 3.7.4 Newcomers or new entrants: this section mixes the terms used in the literature. The EIP-Agri Focus Group and the H2020 Newbee project focus on farming only (Sutherland, Helms, EIP-Agri); while several of the other authors reflect more broadly on the term (inhabitants of rural areas). The use of the two terms (rural attractiveness vs attractiveness of farming) is not yet fully clear in the other sections of the document. In particular, the role of farmers needed in rural areas for food production other than social farming and niche marketing including ecosystem services is insufficient.</p>	<p>No action needed as it is based on WP1 task T1.1. In subsection 3.8.4 a broad interpretation of new entrants added.</p>
<p>The deliverable includes a very basic interpretations of qualitative research, e.g. p. 11 'inductive data analysis is used to conduct qualitative research'. Content analysis needs to be explained a little - literature reviews in qualitative social science do not necessarily follow the process outlined on p. 13. Use of the word 'methodology' is incorrect - a methodology is an overall framing. What is being described on p. 13 refers to the parameters of the systematic review.</p>	<p>No action needed. Methodology was explained and will be updated in coming deliverables.</p>

<p>3.8 Social innovation (social enterprise): this sections emphasises that authors and citations mainly come from the Nordic Baltic (Norway, Finland, Lithuania) and the North-Western (Netherlands, Germany, UK) context where social capital and innovation in rural areas is not necessarily connected with the agri-food sector. In the Mediterranean and Balkan countries, this is different because the connection of rural development/social innovation is mutually connected with small-holder or medium-size family farming. It will be helpful in particular for the teams in the southern and eastern pilots if the D1.1 team will reflect on this cultural context of the authors and their selected sources. They can explain the impact of this (well-known) northern- European perspective, and take into account the different role in other EU areas. Again, the role of the attractiveness of farming in general (arable, dairy, wine, fruit, meat production etc.) and related questions of the farming industries' competition regarding access to land and skilled work.</p>	<p>No action needed as the concept analysed here is a broad view and there is no link to any region.</p>
<p>Other specific points include: The analysis of quality of life (18-20) is rather poorly structured. This project could in fact offer an interesting insight into what this is and how it can be improved. This is a missed opportunity. Offering digital services in rural areas is hampered by poor broadband and this is a major issue that threatens to limit growth and development of SMEs. p.22 rural assets diagram is not fully convincing - how is the human aspect different from anthropic? Interesting that the built environment does not feature. This analysis would be enhanced by recognition of wider debates on multi-functional rural areas and the creation of public goods. (Public goods are discussed on p. 25, but it reads rather as a bolt on to the rest of the narrative. Multi-functionality is discussed later p.30).</p>	<p>This was clarified in the revised version. Structure of section 3.3 QL improved, text added. The human aspect different from anthropic explained in the text. Public goods and multi-functionality are context therefor discussed in different subsections.</p>
<p>Commodification of the countryside is not just about urban dwellers wishing to pay more for the value of certain goods (p. 30), it is about being able to create value out of goods that may have not had a monetary value before.</p>	<p>This cites are contextual with tourism. No amendment is required.</p>
<p>P. 34 'Local food systems (LFSs) and short food chains (SFCs) are based on multifunctionality concept.' This is a puzzling statement??</p>	<p>This statement is deleted</p>
<p>p. 37 - people in urban areas also have well developed social networks.</p>	<p>This statement is deleted</p>
<p>The role of the LEADER programme in advancing the concepts embedded within the idea of social innovation is not really explored.</p>	<p>The text supplemented in the section 3.5. Knowledge and innovation</p>
<p>All needs a thorough check for English language, e.g. p. 50 -Johanis, a 29-year-old urban worker who has just inherited some urban land from his diseased parents - I think this should be deceased?</p>	<p>This was corrected</p>
<p>How are newcomers defined? Page 28, 40 used interchangeably with new entrants (but earlier used in a way that suggests it relates to migrants). Section 3.7.4 is particularly confused and confusing, mixing the work of lifestyle migration, counterurbanisation and new entrants to agriculture.</p>	<p>No actions needed as the concept analysed and included different dimensions. In subsection 3.8.4 Newcomers or new entrants broad interpretation of new entrants added.</p>
<p>This statement on p. 41 is simply not true: Multifunctional agriculture is the key for newcomers.</p>	<p>This statement is deleted</p>
<p>Some very basic interpretations of qualitative research, e.g. p. 11 'inductive data analysis is used to conduct qualitative research'.</p>	<p>No action needed. Methodology was explained and will be updated in coming deliverables.</p>

<p>Content analysis needs to be explained a little - literature reviews in qualitative social science do not necessarily follow the process outlined on p. 13. Use of the word 'methodology' is incorrect - a methodology is an overall framing. What is being described on p. 13 refers to the parameters of the systematic review.</p>	
<p>P.19 - offers one version of the 'rural' - of depopulation etc. But rural is differentiated and some rural areas do not suffer from population decline (especially relevant to those areas that are not remote). Further on p. 20 the reference to cheap housing in rural areas is not necessarily the case for very desirable rural communities that one might find in Belgium or parts of Germany for instance. OECD has published quite a lot of work on the classification of rural areas.</p>	<p>Text added on different rurality in section 3.1 and 3.3.</p>

Table 20 Responses to the monitors' comments